

BIOBUILD

Thermal Solutions for Green Buildings

Deliverable D1.1

Specific climate considerations and building typological classification

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List of terms and definitions

Terms	Definition
End-users needs	Any need that has been expressed by first responders or similar profession, public or private.
Gap (standardisation gap)	Any need that cannot be covered, fully or partially, by an existing standard.
Opportunity	Any item such as a document, existing standards, standards under development, a workshop agreement or even a technological solution that can address a particular need and could facilitate the process of pre-standardisation.
Standard	Technical document designed to be used as a guide, a guideline, a definition or even a rule. https://www.cen.eu/work/endev/whatisen/pages/default.aspx
Thermal comfort	<p>Thermal comfort is generally regarded as the desirable or positive condition of mind a person experiences in relation to how warm or cold a person feels. Thus, it is highly related to the environment which the person is located in. Despite the name, it not only affects comfort, but also productivity and even health and well-being, so satisfaction with the thermal environment is very important¹.</p> <p>In the ISO 7730 standard three comfort tasks (A–C) are defined on the basis of PPD thresholds related either to global comfort or to local discomfort issues. The higher the PPD value, the greater the range of variation allowed for the microclimatic parameter.</p> <p>In the ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55, the thermal comfort is define as the condition of mind that expresses satisfaction with the thermal environment and is assessed by subjective evaluation.</p> <p>Factors that can affect thermal comfort:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Furniture: The furniture in a space can affect the thermal comfort by producing air paths that can focus draughts into occupied areas. The seating can also have an effect on the heat losses from the occupants due to the added insulation afforded by the seat and back of the seating installed. • Age: The age of the occupants has an effect on the activity levels and heat produced and for buildings with children in them, their ages will affect the overall surface area and therefore the total heat into the occupied area. • Personal preference: People have personal preferences for thermal comfort – not everyone will have the same level of comfort in the same environment, even if personal factors such as activity and clothing levels are the same. When the occupants are able to adjust themselves the environmental factors, i.e., temperature and air speed, they feel more satisfied in comparison to the case when the environment is adjusted automatically although the effect of actual temperature and air speed is identical. This is an important factor which is often neglected in the design and management of buildings.
Thermal dissatisfaction	Can be caused by unwanted cooling or heating of one particular part of the body. This is also known as local discomfort. The most common causes of local discomfort are draught, abnormally high vertical temperature difference

¹ David H.C. Chow, in Reference Module in Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences, 2022

	between the head and ankles, too warm or too cool floor or too high radiant temperature asymmetry. ²
Acceptable thermal environment	An environment in which at least 80% of the occupants would find the conditions thermally acceptable ³ .
Residential building	<p>Type of structure primarily designed and constructed to serve as a dwelling place for individuals and families. These buildings are intended for residential use and provide a place for people to live, sleep, and carry out their daily activities. Residential buildings can come in various forms, sizes, and architectural styles.</p> <p>Common types of residential buildings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single-Family Homes: These are standalone houses designed to accommodate a single family or household. They often have their own yards or outdoor spaces and offer a high degree of privacy. Single-family homes come in various styles, from ranch-style to colonial, and can vary in size and layout. • Duplexes and Triplexes: Duplexes are residential buildings divided into two separate housing units, while triplexes have three units. Each unit typically has its own entrance and may share common walls. These are often used for small-scale multi-family living or as investment properties. • Townhouses: Townhouses are typically multi-story homes with shared walls between units. They form a row of homes and can vary in size from small to large. Townhouses often have communal amenities like shared green spaces or parking areas. • Apartment Buildings: Apartment buildings consist of multiple individual apartments within a single structure. They can range from low-rise buildings with a few stories to high-rise skyscrapers with many floors. Apartments may offer various amenities like fitness centres, laundry facilities, and communal spaces. • Condominiums (Condos): Condominiums are similar to apartments in structure but differ in ownership. Each condo unit is individually owned by the occupant, and common areas and amenities are shared and managed by a condominium association. Condo owners pay fees for maintenance and upkeep of these shared spaces.
Non-residential building	A building, or portion thereof, used for a purpose other than a dwelling.
Climate change	<p>Is a long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth's local, regional and global climate. These changes have a broad range of observed effects that are synonymous with the term.</p> <p>Changes observed in Earth's climate since the mid-20th century are driven by human activities, particularly fossil fuel burning, which increases heat-trapping greenhouse gas levels in Earth's atmosphere, raising Earth's average surface temperature. Natural processes, which have been overwhelmed by human activities, can also contribute to climate change, including internal variability (e.g., cyclical ocean patterns like El Niño, La Niña and the Pacific Decadal Oscillation) and external forces (e.g., volcanic activity, changes in the Sun's energy output, and variations in Earth's orbit).⁴</p>
Global warming	<p>Is the long-term heating of Earth's surface observed since the pre-industrial period (between 1850 and 1900) due to human activities, primarily fossil fuel burning, which increases heat-trapping greenhouse gas levels in Earth's atmosphere. This term is not interchangeable with the term "climate change." [26].</p>

² Annex A from ISO 7730:2005 provides examples of local and overall thermal comfort requirements for different categories of environment and types of space.

³ Encyclopaedia of Energy, 2004 Edition, Pages 55-64

⁴ <https://climate.nasa.gov/what-is-climate-change/>

Bio-based material	A material intentionally made from substances derived from living (or once-living) organisms. These materials are sometimes referred to as biomaterials, but this word also has another meaning. Strictly the definition could include many common materials such as wood and leather, but it typically refers to modern materials that have undergone more extensive processing. Unprocessed materials may be called biotic material. Bio-based materials or biomaterials fall under the broader category of bio-products or bio-based products, which includes materials, chemicals and energy derived from renewable biological resources. Bio-based materials are often biodegradable, but this is not always the case. ⁵
Nearly zero-emission building (NZEB)	A building that has a very high energy performance, with nearly zero or very low amount of energy required that should be covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby. According to the revised directive's (Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings (recast)), a zero emission building is defined as a building with a very high energy performance, with very low amount of energy still required fully covered by energy from renewable sources and without on-site carbon emissions from fossil fuels. The ZEB requirement should apply as of 1 January 2030 to all new buildings, and as of 1 January 2027 to all new buildings occupied or owned by public authorities.
Temperature cycle	Variable temperature with a given amplitude and frequency EN ISO 7730:2005.
Carbon footprint:	The sum of all GHG emissions of a given product, asset, or activity.
Greenhouse gas (GHG)	Any gas in the atmosphere which absorbs and re-emits heat. The main GHGs are water vapour, carbon dioxide (CO ₂), methane (CH ₄) and nitrous oxide (N ₂ O).
End-of-life carbon	Emissions which occur after a building or infrastructure project's lifetime – whether associated with deconstruction/demolition, transport from the site, waste processing, or disposal.
Life-cycle assessment (LCA)	A science-based method of assessing the potential environmental impacts associated with a product throughout its life-cycle. When applied to a building, it is referred to as building LCA.
U-value	Thermal transmittance, also known as U-value, is the rate of transfer of heat through a structure (which can be a single material or a composite), divided by the difference in temperature across that structure. The units of measurement are W/m ² K. The better-insulated a structure is, the lower the U-value will be.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AC	Air conditioning
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
ASI	Austrian Standards International
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials

⁵ BIOBASED MATERIALS, CURRAN, M. A. BIOBASED MATERIALS. Kirk-Othmer Encyclopaedia of Chemical Technology, ISBN: 9780471238966. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, NJ, 1-19, (2010).

AT	Air Temperature
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electro-technical Standardisation
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DDs	Degree Days
DBT	Dry-bulb Temperature
EC	European Commission
EGD	European Green Deal
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration. A third-party verified report of the LCA results of a product.
EUROSTAT	EUROSTAT is the statistical office of the European Union, responsible for publishing high-quality Europe-wide statistics and indicators that enable comparisons between countries and regions.
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HDD	Heating Degree Day
ISO	International Standardization Organization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
METEONORM	METEONORM software delivers global historical hourly values of irradiation, temperature, humidity, wind and precipitation from 2010 to present, constantly updated. Meteonorm is a unique combination of reliable data sources and sophisticated calculation tools. It provides access to typical years and historical time series. Meteonorm generates accurate and representative typical years for any place on Earth.
NZEB	Nearly Zero-Emission Building
PMV	Predicted Man Vote ⁶
PPD	Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied
RH	Relative Humidity
SDO	Standard Development Organisation
SHGC	Solar Heat Gain Coefficient
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SR	Solar Radiation
UHI	Urban Heat Island
WP	Work Package
WBT	Wet-bulb Temperature

⁶ *PMV* and *PPD* are terms introduced by Povl Ole Fanger (16 July 1934 – 20 September 2006, was an expert in the field of thermal comfort and perception of indoor environments). He hypothesized that human thermal comfort was based on one's skin temperature and sweat secretion and that one could only be considered 'comfortable' if these two factors were balanced within a narrow range of acceptability. Also ISO 7730:2005 give methods for determination of *PMV* and *PPD*. The *PMV* and *PPD* express warm and cold discomfort for the body as a whole.

1. Introduction

Currently, buildings in Europe account for 40% of energy use and about 95% of the binders used in wood-fibre composites are fossil-derived. Non-biobased materials (e.g. bricks, concrete, plastic, gypsum, glass and rock wool) have high environmental footprints, limited recycling possibilities and should be replaced with bio-based, sustainable materials.

BIOBUILD project, funded by the Horizon Europe programme, focuses on the use of bio-composites to develop non-toxic and zero-pollution building materials with an energy storage functionality. It will incorporate bio-based phase change materials (bioPCM) into solid wood, wood fibres and particles bound by plant oil resins, lignin, or fungal mycelium. The products will be fully recyclable and sustainable without toxic compounds.

The transition towards climate neutrality as set out in the European Green Deal (EGD) calls for innovative and rapid changes. The BIOBUILD project will pave the way to further achieve the EGD goals and speed up innovation in buildings, contributing to a wider use of bio-based materials and expanding the bio-based market to benefit civil society and the environment. The sustainable bio-based materials and technologies will potentially contribute to the imminent transition to decarbonisation in major industrial sectors.

BIOBUILD project aims to achieve the following main objectives:

- Incorporating the bioPCMs into the cells of solid wood, wood particles, virgin and recycled wood fibres by impregnation and in addition optimize the bioPCMs uptake to eliminate leaching;
- Developing and manufacturing three bio-binders for wood-based composites with bioPCM using a) polymerizable plant oils, b) lignin, and c) fungal mycelia;
- Demonstrating the above technologies by production of wood composites with bioPCM as building material (wallboards) and wood flooring (parquet) with improved thermal performance;
- Demonstrating wood construction prototype buildings with integrated novel wallboards and parquet and evaluate the energy-saving performance in Sweden and Spain;
- Employing ex-ante life cycle assessment (LCA) for each product and investigate long-term recyclability to ensure that the materials meet improved sustainability, circularity, and safety standards;
- Engaging in clustering activities with other European projects and initiatives of relevance;
- Determining the industrial, environmental, social and economic challenges and benefits of the new technologies to facilitate their market uptake and transferability to other bio-based materials.

T1.1 Specific climate considerations and building typological classification, aims to define the building typologies and the climatic zones where BIOBUILD concept can be integrated.

Data from the EU standards Directive (i.e. Directive (EU) 2018/844), literature, and EU projects will be used to identify the building requirements and identify reference-building typologies for both residential and not residential sector in different zones of Europe. The outcome of this task will be used as a base for the simulations to prove the replicability of BIOBUILD concept and for the activity related to LCA and integration studies.

D1.1 Specific climate considerations and building typological classification will identify building requirements and reference-building typologies for both residential and not residential (office buildings) sector in the climate zones of Europe.

The main results of this deliverable are:

- Building typologies taking in consideration the climatic zones in Europe for the needs of the project;
- End users needs in the area of climate comfort in residential and office buildings;
- Climatic condition and energy efficiency of residential and office buildings;
- Existing standards in the area of bio composite used in building materials and related fields (focusing on flooring, walls and ceiling);

- Potential gaps in existing standards, based on the correlation of needs of end-users and existing standards;
- Recommendations for future standardisation, based on the identified gaps and existing opportunities;
- General environmental benchmarks for buildings, in the area of the project.

Understanding the link between the energy-efficiency of buildings and climatic conditions can improve the design of energy-efficient housing. Due to global climate change and growing requirements for building energy-efficiency, the number of publications on climate in buildings has grown over the last 20 years. This report attempted to give an up-to-date assessment of the scientific literature in the field of climate mapping for buildings on a global and national scale, filling in the gaps of previous works and focusing on details that were not presented before.

There were over 30 scientific sources examined. The most dominant climate zoning variables were thoroughly analysed. A clear categorization of climate zoning methods with specific criteria was shown. The most used methods were evaluated, emphasizing their similarities and differences, as well as their essential components and advantages. The existence of many climate zoning methods can be an indicator of the lack of agreement on the most effective strategy.

People are becoming more conscious about the link between energy use and environmental impacts as global warming and climate change progress more significantly.

The present energy-related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are around 40 Gt CO₂ equivalent, according to the International Energy Agency. The building industry was directly or indirectly responsible for nearly 50% of global energy consumption and 37% of total GHG emissions in 2021 [1].

Decarbonizing the buildings sector by 2050 is critical to delivering these emission cuts – and to addressing the wider triple planetary crisis of climate change, nature and biodiversity loss, and pollution and waste. However, as the 2022 Buildings Global Status Report shows, the sector is not making the deep systemic changes needed to get on the path to this goal [1].

Several factors can influence building energy consumption: building location and design, occupant behaviour, energy management of the building, climate, and socioeconomic and legal-related characteristics [2]. The issue of the energy demand of buildings is quite complex; however, speaking of the impact of climate on buildings, it can confidently be said that with other factors being equal, changes in climate characteristics significantly influence building energy consumption. A wide range of climate variables, including outdoor air temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, degree-days, wind, etc., impact buildings' thermal performance [2]. However, specific types of buildings are influenced by climate variables differently. Climate, for example, does not affect large venue buildings' extreme daily heating or cooling energy usage, but for commercial buildings, daily excessive heating energy consumption is closely connected to maximum and minimum AT, dry-bulb temperature (DBT), and SR [3]. In contrast, for residential buildings, only DBT has an impact. The wet-bulb temperature (WBT) is the primary impacting climatic parameter for the extreme cooling energy consumption of commercial buildings, which indicates that the combination of AT and RH influences the cooling energy consumption [3]. For many building types, the DBT significantly impacts hourly severe heating energy consumption, followed by the WBT. In contrast, cooling energy consumption is closely connected to the WBT for commercial buildings or has no apparent relationship to climate for large venue buildings [3]. However, the exact mechanism by which climate influences the amount of energy that buildings consume is a complicated, contentious, and highly studied topic in the scientific community.

The document is divided in five chapters and three annexes. A brief overview of the deliverable structure is provided hereafter:

- Chapter 1 is an introductory section of the document and a general overview of the deliverable.
- Chapter 2 is the methodological approach for the analysis and identification of recommendations.
- Chapter 3 addressed to building typological classification on specific climate consideration.
- Chapter 4 is devoted to a selection of the cities to characterize the different climate zones and building typology. The cities were selected in order to cover the five climate zones according to the classification done by ECOFYS according to the report "Towards nearly zero-energy buildings".

- Chapter 5 identify and presents the existing standards, including identification of standardisation gaps and consequently of potential standardisation items that can be explored in the framework of the project.
- Chapter 6 describes general environmental benchmarks for buildings.
- Chapter 7 summarises the basic conclusions of the analysis and recommendations based for the other WPs.

Annex 1 presents the list of identified European standards.

Annex 2 presents the list of identified International standards.

2. Approach and methodology

It is agreed that good documentation is important to the success of R&I projects, and BIOBUILD is not an exception. In this regard, the authors of the report intended to identify, select and collect a helpful enough documentation for the other WPs of the project (especially WP2 and WP6) that should be able to rely on it.

Usually, the problems related to documentation can be solved by understanding how documentation works, and that there are four distinct kinds of documentation – with four distinct functions. The four kinds of documentation are:

- learning-oriented tutorials;
- goal-oriented how-to guides;
- understanding-oriented discussions;
- information-oriented reference material.

Structuring documentation according to its four distinct functions contributes to D1.1 to ensure that each of them is adequately served. It also makes it far easier to write and maintain. D1.1 also use the two most common types of documentation used in research: note citations and parenthetical citations.

Three major topics were analysed:

- buildings typology classification taking in consideration specific climate zone: dry, mild and continental climate (according with Köppen climate classification system);
- identification and brief analyse of existing standards in the area of the project (bio materials and methodologies for flooring, walls, ceilings etc.);
- environmental benchmarks for building: LCA approaches, climatic constrained.

Another way to group the data is by assigning a regional distribution to the countries that participate in BIOBUILD. As the project deals with building construction materials research, and hence climatological differences between regions may affect priorities between countries from different geographical regions. This report contains information on past and current research with a focus on EU funded projects and programmes. Important non-EU funded pan-European, regional and international initiatives of relevance are also included in the overview.

This report also included information from existing International and European standard, and other standard, like ASTM or ASHRAE standards.

Building typology classification refers to building and documenting buildings according to their essential characteristics. In architectural discourse, typological classification tends to focus on building function (use), building form, or architectural style.

In our project the D1.1 take in consideration the specific climate zone for building typology.

The typologies consist of the following elements:

- a classification concept for existing residential buildings according to specific climate consideration and further parameters;
- a set of example buildings (use cases), residential buildings and small office buildings;
- typical energy consumption values for the use cases buildings, taking in consideration the new materials with thermal function from the project;
- showcase calculations of the possible energy savings;
- statistical data for buildings and supply systems.

A building classification is necessary for strategically collecting information on case study buildings in order to develop risk management strategies and a decision support system. Besides, it provides the basis for the building simulation being carried out during the project.

Standards are qualified recommendations which are developed by consensus among technical experts who are nominated by interested parties and other stakeholders. They are not a source of law but document the state of the art at the time of their development. Standards can for example determine requirements for a specific item, material, component, system or service. Other types of standards can for example describe a certain method or procedure. By ensuring the compatibility of components, products and services, standards facilitate international trade. Gap is any need that cannot be covered, fully or partially, by an existing standard. Gaps like needs and standards can be generic or specific. Gaps are identified and analysed in Chapter 5 of this document.

Environmental benchmark for buildings, energy-efficient construction is an important factor for better climate protection. Affordable housing and at the highest energy standards do not have to be a contradiction in terms.

Supporting European policies related to the efficient use of resources in construction and its major goal is the development of a performance-based approach for sustainable design, enabling to assess resource efficiency of buildings in the early stages of building design.

In the proposed approach the performance of a building, focussing on resource use, is benchmarked against existing standard and/or best practices, in the area of LCA. The work will be continued in the following WPs, especially in WP6.

The steps of the work carried out for D1.1 are presented in more detail in the following:

- The first step (STEP 1) is the collection of data, including the collection of results of other completed or on-going EU projects, for three pillars:
 - Pillar 1: existing building typologies and relevant end-user's needs for the project deliverables.
 - Pillar 2: existing standards and identified relevant gaps with the project deliverables.
 - Pillar 3: existing opportunities relevant to environmental benchmark to buildings.
- The second step (STEP 2) is the analysis and the homogenisation of the data. Data from other projects are structured in a different way compared to BIOBUILD. In order to have a good overview of existing information, gaps and standards and needs, already identified in previous projects, it was necessary to study and homogenise them in a new scheme.
- The third step (STEP 3) is the analysis conducted using the results from pillar 1 and 2.
- The fourth step (STEP 4) is the matching of the analyses results and the gaps in order to provide some initial recommendations to the next stages of the project.

3. Building typological classification on specific climate consideration

Existing climate classifications are mostly concerned with vegetation growth and are therefore not adequate for investigating the interaction between outdoor and indoor climate and its influence on the building envelope.

In order to define climate zones appropriate for energy saving building's needs, indoor target criteria have to be considered, such as thermal comfort and acceptable thermal environment. Therefore, relative humidity and temperature are chosen as key criteria having the greatest influence on using new materials. Accordingly, Europe is divided into three climatic zones applying an overlay of these two parameters. The definition of climate zones guarantees that the most representative and crucial data from the various buildings serving as case studies is collected. Hence, for each climate zone at least one building category will be required.

3.1 Köppen classification system

Climate is the long-term pattern of weather in a particular area. Weather can change from hour-to-hour, day-to-day, month-to-month or even year-to-year. A region's weather patterns, usually tracked for at least 30 years, are considered its climate.

Climate is determined by a region's climate system. A climate system has five major components: the atmosphere, the hydrosphere, the cryosphere, the land surface, and the biosphere.

Topography and vegetation influence climate by helping determine how the Sun's energy is used on Earth. The abundance of plants and the type of land cover (such as soil, sand, or asphalt) impacts evaporation and ambient temperature.

Climate is not uniform. Small variations, called microclimates, exist in every climate region. Microclimates are largely influenced by topographic features such as lakes, vegetation, and cities. In large urban areas, for example, streets and buildings absorb heat from the sun, raising the average temperature of the city higher than average temperatures of more open areas nearby. This is known as the "urban heat island effect."

In 1948, the American climatologist Charles Thornthwaite developed a climate classification system that scientists still use today. Thornthwaite's system relies on a region's water budget and potential evapotranspiration. Potential evapotranspiration describes the amount of water evaporated from a vegetated piece of land. Indices such as humidity and precipitation help determine a region's moisture index. The lower its moisture index value, the more arid a region's climate.

The major classifications in Thornthwaite's climate classification are microthermal, mesothermal, and megathermal.

Although many climatologists think the Thornthwaite system is an efficient, rigorous way of classifying climate, it is too complex and its mapping is difficult. The system is rarely used outside scientific publishing.

The most popular system of classifying climates was proposed in 1900 by Russian-German scientist Wladimir Köppen. He observed that the type of vegetation in a region depended largely on climate. Studying vegetation, temperature, and precipitation data, he and other scientists developed a system for naming the climate regions. According to the Köppen climate classification system, there are five climate groups: tropical, dry, mild, continental, and polar. These climate groups are further divided into climate types. The following list shows the climate groups and their types:

- Tropical
 - Wet (rainforest)
 - Monsoon
 - Wet and dry (savanna)
- Dry
 - Arid
 - Semiarid

- Mild
 - Mediterranean
 - Humid subtropical
 - Marine
- Continental
 - Warm summer
 - Cool summer
 - Subarctic (boreal)
- Polar
 - Tundra
 - Ice cap

On the other hand, outdoor microclimates vary among different urban neighbourhoods depending on their morphological variations. The Local Climate Zone (LCZ) framework is a well-developed typological morphological classification used to capture the variation that characterises neighbourhood microclimates. However, it does not include detailed morphological parameters within neighbourhoods that have synergistic effects on microclimates. It is thus essential to develop neighbourhood typologies with detailed spatial descriptions.

Parameters which are not covered by the LCZs usually are analysed too, including building block's floor area ratio and shape factor, street canyon's orientation and Height-to-Width ratio, street total length, green space area, and tree cover ratio. The generalised neighbourhood typologies can be used as the basis for design interventions aiming at climate adaptation in heat-prone urban areas.

For the BIOBUILD project the following climate groups are taken in consideration:

- Mild
 - Mediterranean
 - Humid subtropical
 - Marine
- Continental
 - Warm summer
 - Cool summer
 - Subarctic (boreal)

Figure 1. Köppen-Geiger climate classification map of Europa [6].

Figure 2. Distribution of the climate zones (FCZ codes) within Europe [4].

According to Köppen-Geiger climate classification, there are four prevailing climatic zones in Europe: Table 1 combined with Figure 1.

Colour	Zone	Description
Yellow	Csa	Temperate with dry, hot summer (Mediterranean climate).
Green	Cfb	Temperate without dry season and warm summer.
Light blue	Dfb	Temperate continental climate/humid continental climate without dry season.
Dark blue	Dfc	Cold, without dry season and with cold summer.

Some countries may have more than one climatic zone and it is sometimes difficult to establish the prevailing climate classification of Köppen.

3.2 Existing typology concept

Climate classification is essential for buildings because it influences the planning and design of a building, its orientation, building geometry and design of building envelopes such as walls, roofs and openings. Generally speaking, in the event of climate change, the existing classifications must be revised or updated to provide both proper guidelines for the design and construction of buildings and adaptation strategies for the existing buildings.

The weather parameters such as temperature, moisture, precipitation, wind and solar radiation define the climate of a geographical location. Each location has its climatic features based on the earth's latitude, longitude, and altitude with a specific range of weather parameters.

Some locations are extremely cold, some are hot, some are warm, and some are humid. It is essential to look at the outdoor climatic conditions while designing a building as it decides the thermal comfort indoors, especially free-running or naturally ventilated building. Therefore, a designer should study a given location's prevalent weather conditions, referred to as 'site analyses' in the architectural design process. Most building codes have considered climate and its various parameters, including zone classification, to arrive at the respective guidelines. Climate zones were originally devised to examine ecology, plant and building sciences. Several types of climate classification are currently in use worldwide for many purposes.

The climate classifications have been valid and adapted since they evolved. However, with the advent of climate change, the validity of existing climate classification is questionable. According to IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change), Special report of 2018 [7] "human induced warming reached approximately 1.0°C (likely between 0.8 and 1.2°C) above pre-industrial levels in 2017, increasing at the rate of 0.2°C (likely between 0.1 and 0.3°C) per decade (high confidence)". It is also reported with high confidence that warming higher than the global average has been experienced already in many places, with higher average over land than the ocean. One of the main sectors responsible for the acceleration of climate change and the depletion of natural resources is the construction industry. This industry is responsible for using 40-50% of the Earth's energy and increasing the anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases. In this context, D1.1 considered essential to study regional climates in order to foresee the adverse effects of the construction materials proposed and recommend appropriate measures to avoid or minimise the damage that can be caused in the small and medium term. It is important to balance the climatic zones assigned to a given region and the building that will take place, thereby prioritising the construction that adapts to the climatic conditions of the area, mitigates the adverse effects of climate zone and has the potential to adapt to possible changes in the weather.

Climate and the environment where the building is located, will affect the conditions to which the building is exposed to, and therefore will determine its thermal behaviour and final energy consumption. The thermal behaviour of the building at the same time, will condition the final selection of technologies, materials, concepts or refurbishment techniques to be used in facades or inside of the building in order to guarantee their energy efficiency.

When the energy consumption of buildings is analysed, it is convenient to analyse whether the specific energy use of the building is climate dependant or not. The climate dependant variables are those that affect the specific energy consumption of the building, which is increased when climate becomes more severe.

Among the different parameters that will affect the building space heating and cooling, climate, local environment, type of building and its use- or its internal indoor activity – may be mentioned.

The climate conditions that mainly affect the energy consumption, of a building are:

- external air temperature;
- wind velocity and direction;
- solar radiation;
- Infrared radiation.

Climatic zones with similar characteristics (outside temperature, solar radiation) will be established in order to determine the most appropriate technologies for each use cases from BIOBUILD project, of different European regions.

In order to reach D1.1 objectives we have combined the Köppen-Geiger classification with the European Heat Index, the European Cooling Index and the NZEB zoning. This actually gives a new NZEB zoning map.

Climate borders are different from political borders. So, in several countries, there will be different climate zones for NZEB and this could lead to an update of the local rules.

The new European Heating Index (EHI) is developed to make a more consistent system for Europe. The degree-day method shows that there are 10 times more degree-days in Kiruna (North of Sweden) than in Palermo. But the heat demand in Kiruna is not ten times higher due to the different insulation of the buildings. So, the EHI has been developed with this in mind.

The index is normalized, where 100 is equal to an average European condition. Using a reference degree-day number of 2600, corresponding to an annual average outdoor temperature just above 10°C, fulfils this normalization. Strasbourg in France is the typical space heating city in Europe, with a heating index of 100. In the same way as for the new European heating index (EHI), a new European cooling index has been constructed based on the same principles. First, it is assumed that the outdoor temperature is the predominating factor for the heating and cooling demand.

Furthermore, it is assumed that the heating demand (and not the cooling demand) is the predominating factor for building insulation. Therefore, the same approach as for the EHI has been used. [9].
The ECOHEATCOOL study [11] comprised 80 cities in Europe to develop the EHI and the ECI. The maps (Figure 3 and 4) is not representative for all locations in each country, since the existing data grid consists of only 80 locations, but the information are good enough for our project.

Figure 3. European heating index (EHI) [11].

Figure 4. European cooling index (ECI) [11].

In the construction of the ECI it is also assumed that the cooling systems are designed to maintain an indoor temperature of 22°C only when the outdoor temperature is below 29°C. When the outdoor temperature exceeds this limit, the indoor temperature will start to slide at a constant difference of 7°C below the outdoor temperature [9].

In study [12] the available data of NZEB definitions was grouped according to ECOFYS classification into five European climate zones as shown in Figure 5, in order to study the variation in primary energy values and other relevant parameters within comparable climate zones.

In the report '*Towards nearly zero-energy Buildings*', Ecofys divided European countries in 5 European climate zones based on global radiation, heating's degree-days, cooling degree-days and cooling potential by night ventilation. This overview result in the following European Climate Chart that can be used for different definitions of NZEBs (Table 2).

Map of European climatic zones

Legend	
	Zones 1&2
	Zone 3
	Zone 4
	Zone 5

Figure 5. ECOFYS climate zones suitable for ranking of technology options and comparison of building performance [12].

Table 2 – Building classification in European countries and NZEB typology

Zone	Countries	Köppen	NZEB typology
Zone 1	Cyprus – Greece – South Italy (Catania) – South Spain (Seville).	Csa	Well-insulated building envelope with limited fenestration area; glazing with very low SHGC and shading from direct sunlight in summer; reflective or cool colours exterior envelope surfaces essential (colours with low heat absorption to reduce the solar load during the summer period); solar powered AC equipment can provide day-time cooling; thermal mass and lower night-time temperatures provide comfortable indoor conditions after sunset (nocturnal ventilation).
Zone 2	Portugal – Central Spain (Madrid) – South France (Bouches-du-Rhône) – Central Italy (Lazio).	Csa/Cfb	Well-insulated building envelope with energy efficient fenestration (very low to low U-value, moderate to high SHGC depends on glazing area); operable shading systems required to prevent summer over-heating; thermal mass and balanced ventilation with heat recovery is beneficial. Nocturnal ventilation.
Zone 3	Slovakia – Hungary – Slovenia – North Italy (Lombardia).	Dfb	Moderately insulated building envelope with limited fenestration area having low SHGC and effective shading devices; green (vegetated) roofs and/or reflective exterior envelope surfaces are beneficial; since the removal of latent heat (water vapour) matches the energy required for sensible cooling, investing in sophisticated ventilation is essential to provide healthy and comfortable indoor air conditions without wasting energy.
Zone 4	Netherlands – Germany – Belgium – Denmark – Ireland – North France – Poland.	Cfb/Dfb	Well insulated to moderate insulated building envelope with efficient fenestration area with moderate SHGC and effective shading devices

Zone 5	Baltic countries – Sweden – North Poland.	Dfc	Compact building design with very well- insulated building envelope components; total fenestration area should be limited with very low U-value and high SHGC (solar heat gain coefficient); thermal mass and balanced ventilation with heat recovery is essential
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If we compare the Köppen-Geiger Classification with the study of ECOFYS, we can see that most countries get more or less the same classification, some of the countries are divided between two areas according to Köppen-Geiger.

The north of Italy and the north of Spain have Cfb climate and belong to the climate of zone 4. West Germany belongs to Cfb climate (zone 4) and the east part to Dfb (zone 3). The south of Sweden is much warmer and belongs to Dfb while the middle and north of Sweden belongs to Dfc. In the NZEB zones there is no difference between these two classifications. It can be concluded that the NZEB climates zones are very useful as long as we keep local circumstances in mind.

Heating and cooling degree days

The degree-day method dates back to the early 19th century when it was developed in the USA. In 1927 it was introduced at Bewag in Berlin (S. Werner, Heat load in district heating systems, 1984).

The heating and cooling degree method is a very traditional method that has been in use for decades. It provides an indication of severity of the climate in different locations by documenting when during a given year the external air temperature falls below or rises above a specified temperature, requiring thus heating or cooling. The specific temperature is called base temperature and represents the temperature at which no heating nor cooling loads are required in buildings for that climate. The degree day concept assumes, therefore, that the heat loss factor is constant and is proportional to the temperature difference between indoors and outdoors.

Heating degree days express the severity of the cold over a specific time period taking into consideration outdoor temperature and room temperature. For calculating heating degree days of European cities, weather data were taken from METEONORM and calculated to heating degree days (HDD) using the methodology applied by EUROSTAT, which form a common and comparable basis. External and internal building conditions may require additional energy for cooling and ventilation in order to meet a defined comfort level. This comfort level may be defined in building regulations or be given as user specifications. In order to meet the comfort conditions quantification of the energy for cooling is either based on the number of corresponding Cooling Degrees (similar to the number of Heating Degrees) or resulting from an iterative numeric calculation [9] driven by maintaining the comfort level in the building at a given comfort temperature [10].

Studies demonstrate [10] that when looking at the single measures wall, roof or floor insulation on their own, it is apparent that they contribute in different ways to the savings of the combined insulation measures.

The insulation of a wall of the reference single family house in Seville reduces the cooling energy demand by 4 kWh/m² year. Surprisingly the effect of roof insulation is positive. This is due to the particularly high temperatures of the roof caused by solar radiation which leads to higher surface temperatures and a consequential thermal insulation benefit.

The insulation of the ground-floor results in an increase of cooling demand in hot climates. This is caused by the reduction of the cooling effect because of the relative cool temperatures of the ground in the summer situation. On the other hand, during the winter season the insulation of the ground floor results in heating-energy savings [10].

Therefore, the recommended U-values in [10] take into account the effect of insulation on heating and cooling demand. However, regarding floor insulation further restrictions could be given to meet demands such as the acoustic comfort (contact noise), building physics (level of surface temperature given the humidity conditions in order to avoid condensation or desired fast response-time of floor heating) that might require more insulation (a lower U-value) for floors.

Figure 6. Cooling/heating degree days, according to EUROSTAT [8].

However, regarding floor insulation further restrictions could be given to meet demands such as the acoustic comfort (contact noise), building physics (level of surface temperature given the humidity conditions in order to avoid condensation or desired fast response-time of floor heating) that might require more insulation for floors. Degree-days methods (DDM) are well-known techniques that have been used for decades. It indicates the severity of the climate in various locations by documenting when the external AT falls below or rises above a specified temperature during a given year, necessitating heating or cooling. This method is generally defined as the sum of the temperature differences between the outdoor mean temperature over 24 h and a base temperature daily (with 18°C as the most frequent base temperature value). The base temperature is arbitrary, but it is commonly described as the outside temperature at which heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning (HVAC) systems do not have to operate to keep the building’s internal climate comfortable. According to ASHRAE standard 169 [19], cooling and heating degree-days (CDD, HDD) are calculated according to equations:

$$HDD_t = \sum_{d=1}^{Dt} (T_b - \bar{T})_d^+ \quad (1)$$

$$CDD_t = \sum_{d=1}^{Dt} (\bar{T} - T_b)_d^+ \quad (2)$$

where

T_b — base temperature;

+ — only positive values are considered;

\bar{T} — the mean value of the maximum and minimum temperatures in a given day, as shown in equation (3).

$$\bar{T} = \frac{(T_{max} + T_{min})}{2} \quad (3)$$

3.3 Thermal comfort requirements in formal and informal standards and EU regulations

“Thermal comfort can be defined as a person’s own awareness of the thermal atmosphere, and it is defined as a person’s neutral feeling in relation to a given thermal environment, without sweating”.

From: **Numerical Methods in Environmental Data Analysis, 2022**

Thermal comfort is generally regarded as the desirable or positive condition of mind a person experiences in relation to how warm or cold a person feels. Thus, it is highly related to the environment which the person is located in. Despite the name, it not only affects comfort, but also productivity and even health and well-being, so satisfaction with the thermal environment is very important.

Thermal comfort in built environments is an everyday issue for architects and technicians and one that has been dealt with widely in scientific literature and international and national standards.

Through the use of its complex temperature regulation mechanism, the human body is able to reach a condition of thermal equilibrium with the surrounding environment when the variation of internal energy, S , at the body core level is equal to zero [13].

The thermal exchange between a subject and the environment is equal to the difference between metabolic heat production (apart from the so-called mechanical power) and thermal losses due to respiration and exchanges of heat through the skin surface (nude and clothed areas).

Thermal comfort in buildings can be seen as the outcome of the well-balanced combination of building systems. Thermal comfort in a building can be caused by the location of the building and the activity performed inside the building. The design of the building and the indoor air quality can also affect the thermal comfort (Figure 7).

The heat exchange between the human body and its environment occurs mainly in three ways, namely through:

- radiation;
- convection;
- evaporation.

Thermal indoor environment is affected by both internal and external sources.

Figure 7. Illustration of indoor thermal comfort (Ecophon, 2020) [14].

Common heat sources are usually electrical equipment (such as lighting and computers), sun radiation, and human presence. The common sources of cold are window surfaces, poorly insulated walls, and thermal bridges in the constructions [15].

All these sources will influence the human perception of the environment and therefore the comfort level.

From an architectural point of view, thermal comfort is associated with soft materials and smooth surfaces such as textiles, porous surfaces or even wood. Flat and hard surfaces (made of metal or stone) are on the other hand perceived as less convenient for thermal comfort. Of course this perception is different from person to person.

It's not yet scientifically described what triggers this perception, but one could assume that it relates to the perceived radiative exchange with a given surface. This is described through emissivity. Emissivity ranges from 0 to 1, where glossy, metallic surfaces show an emissivity close to 0, and matt surfaces are close to 1.

The International Organization for Standardization Standard **ISO 7730** [17] introduces also the concept of thermal comfort categories. In the ISO 7730 standard three different comfort tasks (A–C) are defined on the basis of PPD thresholds related either to global comfort or to local discomfort issues. The higher the PPD value, the greater the range of variation allowed for the microclimatic parameter.

Tables 3, 4 and 5 show values for the local thermal discomfort causes by vertical air temperature difference, warm/cold floor and radiant temperature asymmetry, according with SR EN ISO 7730:2006 [17].

Table 3 – Vertical air temperature difference between head and ankles

Category	Vertical air temperature difference ^a °C
A	< 2
B	< 3
C	< 4

^a 1,1 and 0,1 m above floor.

Table 4 – Range of floor temperature

Category	Floor surface temperature range °C
A	19 to 29
B	19 to 29
C	17 to 31

Table 5 – Radiant temperature asymmetry

Category	Radiant temperature asymmetry °C			
	Warm ceiling	Cool wall	Cool ceiling	Warm wall
A	< 5	< 10	< 14	< 23
B	< 5	< 10	< 14	< 23
C	< 7	< 13	< 18	< 35

The standard ISO 7730 shows also design criteria reproduced in Table 6 (especially for office building) that are derived under certain assumptions. For the thermal environment, the criteria for the operative temperature are based on typical levels of activity, e.g., for clothing of 0.5 clo⁷ during summer ("cooling season") and 1.0 clo

⁷ The insulation effect of clothes can be measured in the unit "Icl, Clo" – where:

1 Clo = 0.155 m²K/W

Clo = 0 - corresponds to a naked person

Clo = 1 - corresponds to the insulating value of clothing needed to maintain a person in comfort sitting at rest in a room at 21°C with air movement of 0.1 m/s and humidity less than 50% - typically a person wearing a business suit.

during winter (“heating season”). The criteria for the mean air velocity apply for a turbulence intensity of approximately 40% (mixing ventilation). The design criteria are valid for the occupancy conditions as given, but could also be applicable to other types of spaces used in similar ways.

Table 6 – Example design criteria for spaces in various types of building

Type of building/space	Activity W/m ²	Category	Operative temperature °C		Maximum mean air velocity ^a m/s	
			Summer (cooling season)	Winter (heating season)	Summer (cooling season)	Winter (heating season)
Single office Landscape office	70	A	24,5 ± 1,0	22,0 ± 1,0	0,12	0,10
Conference room Auditorium		B	24,5 ± 1,5	22,0 ± 2,0	0,19	0,16
Cafeteria/restaurant Classroom		C	24,5 ± 2,5	22,0 ± 3,0	0,24	0,21 ^b
Kindergarten	81	A	23,5 ± 1,0	20,0 ± 1,0	0,11	0,10 ^b
		B	23,5 ± 2,0	22,0 ± 2,5	0,18	0,15 ^b
		C	23,5 ± 2,5	22,0 ± 3,5	0,23	0,19 ^b
Department store	93	A	23,0 ± 1,0	19,0 ± 1,5	0,16	0,13 ^b
		B	23,0 ± 2,0	19,0 ± 3,0	0,20	0,15 ^b
		C	23,0 ± 3,0	19,0 ± 4,0	0,23	0,18 ^b

^a The maximum mean air velocity is based on a turbulence intensity of 40 % and air temperature equal to the operative temperature according to 6.2 and Figure A.2. A relative humidity of 60 % and 40 % is used for summer and winter, respectively. For both summer and winter a lower temperature in the range is used to determine the maximum mean air velocity.

^b Below 20 °C limit (see Figure A.2).

In the **ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55**, thermal comfort is defined as the “*condition of mind that expresses satisfaction with the thermal environment and is assessed by subjective evaluation*”.

ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55: Thermal Environmental Conditions for Human Occupancy is an American National Standard published by ASHRAE that establishes the ranges of indoor environmental conditions to achieve acceptable thermal comfort for occupants of buildings. It was first published in 1966, and since 2004 has been updated every three to six years. The most recent version of the standard was published in 2023. The purpose of the standard is to specify the combinations of indoor thermal environmental factors and personal factors that will produce thermal environmental conditions acceptable to a majority of the occupants within the space. Although the ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55 does not require the evaluation of comfort in an existing building, the standard offers a guideline of performing an evaluation when the evaluation of comfort is required by other codes or standard. Generally, the evaluation of comfort in existing buildings can be performed from two perspectives: from occupant satisfaction survey and physical environmental measurements. Annex B from the standard demonstrates a computer program for calculation of PMV/PPD.

The 2023 edition of ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55, Thermal Environmental Conditions for Human Occupancy, has been updated with major improvements and simplifications to the two sections that make up the heart of the standard: determining satisfactory thermal environment in occupied spaces and compliance documentation. The methods for measuring thermal comfort includes Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) method, Percentage of People Dissatisfied (PPD) method, ASHRAE Standard 55 etc. Fanger⁸'s (the reference nr. should come after “method” PMV method⁸ is commonly [16] used method for objectively evaluating thermal comfort. The PMV method was developed in the 1970 and are based on a constant state model. When a wide number of people were used to a certain temperature, the PMV values represent their average thermal sensation. Six variables that affect a person's thermal comfort must be calculated in order to quantify PMV. Humidity, air velocity, mean

⁸Ole Fanger published PMV and PPD for the evaluation of thermal comfort in 70s by means of study of 1296 subjects. The method is also used by ISO 7730.

radiant temperature, air temperature are four environmental variables, while occupants' metabolic rate and fabric insulation (CLO value) are two personal factors. Fanger's PPD method is the commonly used method for objectively evaluating thermal comfort. The PPD (Percentage of People Dissatisfied) method was developed in the 1970s and are based on a steady state model. ASHRAE Standard 55 necessitates the calculation of air humidity, air velocity and temperature, measuring the mean radiant temperature from three different heights. Environmental factors (temperature, thermal radiation, humidity, and air speed) and personal factors (activity and clothing) combine in complex ways to create indoor thermal conditions, and personal comfort levels vary from one occupant to another. Standard 55 is designed to specify those combinations of factors that result in satisfactory thermal conditions for a majority of occupants, with criteria for evaluating comfort in existing buildings, as well as requirements and calculation procedures for design compliance.

The PMV is an index that predicts the mean value of the votes of a large group of persons on the 7-point thermal sensation scale (see Table 7), based on the heat balance of the human body. Thermal balance is obtained when the internal heat production in the body is equal to the loss of heat to the environment. In a moderate environment, the human thermoregulatory system will automatically attempt to regulate the skin temperature and sweat secretion to maintain heat balance [17].

Table 7 – Seven-point thermal sensation scale [17].

+3	Hot
+2	Warm
+1	Slightly warm
0	Neutral
-1	Slightly cool
-2	Cool
-3	Cold

PMV may be calculated for different combinations of metabolic rate, clothing insulation, air temperature, mean radiant temperature, air velocity and air humidity (see also ISO 7726).

As a part of the European Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), CEN/CENELEC has developed a set of new EPBD standards focussing on aspects directly related to energy performance like methods to calculate energy use, inspection protocols or definition of e.g. climatic (outdoor) conditions. This includes a standard that describes health and comfort related performance criteria that should be used in the context of energy calculations and assessments: '**EN 16798-1:2019** - *Energy performance of buildings – Ventilation for buildings – Part 1: Indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of energy performance of buildings addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting and acoustics – Module M1-6*'. EN 16798-1 is not a harmonised in the EPB standard series but EU member states can use elements such as guideline values from the standard to improve their national building codes. EN 16798-1:2019 replaces EN 15251 and it focusses on parameters at category I, II, III level – sometimes also level IV (level I is best, III / IV is worst) for thermal environment, indoor air quality, lighting and acoustics. The standard explains how to use these parameters for building system design and energy performance calculations. Section 5.2 on the current landscape of European standardization discusses this standard in more detail.

The standard EN 16798-1 recommends an indoor temperature interval for each of comfort category, calculated based on EN ISO 7730. Annex B, table B.2, provides examples of recommended design indoor operative temperatures that are acceptable for different comfort categories and type of buildings. The indoor operative temperature limits can also be defined with adaptive methods considering outdoor temperatures. The technical report of this standard, CEN/TR 16798-2 references some recommended methods for the long-term evaluation of the general thermal comfort conditions in its Annex D. In method A, the thermal comfort is indicated by the number or % of occupied hours when the PMV or the operative temperature is outside a specific range. In method B, degree hours criteria, the time during which the actual operative temperature exceeds the specified range during the occupied hours is weighted by a factor that depends on how many degrees the range has been exceeded. This method is preferred because there is no need to make assumptions for occupant's metabolic rate and fabric insulation.

The **Swiss standard SIA V382/2.15** (SN 546 382 series, now under revision) give an evaluation method of the thermal comfort based on the hourly mean values of the air temperature in the occupied zone, plotted against

the maximum 1 h mean outdoor temperature value of the day. Only the period from April 1 to October 30 and only working hours (7 A.M. to 6 P.M.) are considered.

Apart of the above standards, considered by the authors of this report as the most important, there are other international, European and industrial standards and standardization documents. These will be referred to in the chapter dedicated to standards and standardization activities.

The EU regulations that should be taken in consideration regarding thermal comfort in the residential and non-residential buildings (office buildings):

Regarding the thermal comfort in the non-residential building, it must be considered that the temperatures in the workplace are governed by the Workplace (Health, Safety and Welfare) Regulations 1992, which oblige employers to provide a reasonable temperature in the workplace.

- **Council Directive 89/654/EEC** of 30 November 1989 concerning the minimum safety and health requirements for the workplace (first individual directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).
- Room temperature - During working hours, the temperature in rooms containing workplaces must be adequate for human beings, having regard to the working methods being used and the physical demands placed on the workers.
- The temperature in rest areas, rooms for duty staff, sanitary facilities, canteens and first aid rooms must be appropriate to the particular purpose of such areas.
- Windows, skylights and glass partitions should allow excessive effects of sunlight in workplaces to be avoided, having regard to the nature of the work and of the workplace.
- The **Approved Code of Practice** (Workplace health, safety and welfare. Workplace (Health, Safety and Welfare) Regulations 1992. Approved Code of Practice) suggests a minimum temperature of 16°C or 13°C if work involves severe physical effort. However, these are only guidelines.
- The Health and Safety Executive (HSE) previously defined thermal comfort in the workplace, as: "...roughly between 13°C and 30°C, with acceptable temperatures for more strenuous work activities concentrated towards the bottom end of the range, and more sedentary activities towards the higher end".

However, the complexity of thermal comfort means that there is no meaningful maximum guideline temperature, particularly at higher temperatures.

- **Directive 2010/31/EU** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of the buildings, consolidated version January 2021. This Directive promotes the improvement of the energy performance of buildings within the Union, taking into account outdoor climatic and local conditions, as well as indoor climate requirements and cost-effectiveness.

Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 laying down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products. Consolidated version: 16/07/2021.

- The provisions of this regulation are aimed to:
 - Clarify the affixing of CE marking to construction products.
 - Introduce the need to issue a declaration of performance as a basis for CE marking.
 - Define clear rules for the assessment and verification of constancy of performance (AVCP) systems applicable to construction products (former Attestation of Conformity AoC).
 - Define the role and responsibilities of manufacturers, distributors, importers, notified bodies, technical assessment bodies, market surveillance and Member States' authorities as regards the application of this EU regulation.
 - Introduce simplified procedures enabling cost reductions for businesses, especially SMEs.
 - Provide a clear framework for the harmonised technical specifications (harmonised standards and European Assessment Documents) and a common technical language for construction products.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has always stressed the importance of **indoor air quality (IAQ)** and the potential danger of pollutants emitted from indoor sources; thus, it has become one of the main determinants

for health. In recent years, reference documents and guidelines have been produced on many pollutants in order to:

- decrease their impact on human health (as well as the number of pollutants present in indoor environments), and
- regulate the relevant levels of chemicals that can be emitted from the various materials.

In recent years, several international organizations, e.g., the European Collaborative Action (ECA), the World Health Organization (WHO), and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) have produced reference documents, guidelines, agreements, and protocols. For example, the Parma declaration, the Children's Environment and Health Action Plan for Europe CEHAPE), European Union (EU) regulations; documents, and rules for characterization and determination on many pollutants (e.g., European/international Standards (EN) ISO 16000 – Indoor air quality, European technical specification (CEN/TS) 16516: construction products – determination of emission into indoor air). The purpose of this documentation is to tend to the decrease in the number of pollutants present in indoor environments and to regulate the levels of chemicals that can be emitted from different materials, in order to contain the negative impacts on IAQ.

The WHO has developed guidelines for IAQ, relating to a certain number of pollutants, present indoor, for which scientific knowledge relating to human health effects were considered robust enough. The substances considered are benzene (C₆H₆, CAS number 71-43-2), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂, 10102-44-0), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (especially benzo[a]pyrene BaP, C₂₀H₁₂, 50-32-8) (PAHs), naphthalene (C₁₀H₈, 91-20-3), carbon monoxide (CO, 630-08-0), radon, trichlorethylene (C₂HCl₃, 79-01-6), and tetrachloroethylene (C₂Cl₄, 127-18-4). For carcinogenic pollutants (such as benzene, BaP, trichloroethylene), a unitary risk (UR) is defined for the general population associated with their presence in the air. Alongside these guidelines, mention should be made of those relating to the risks associated with the presence of humidity and biological agents. Furthermore, for the purpose of risk assessment, it is of particular importance to consider not only the guide value or reference parameter, but also other fundamental elements, such as the vulnerability of the population and the exposure conditions.

There is no specific reference directive on IAQ in European legislation, although pre-legislative initiatives have multiplied over the years. For example, indoor air quality and its impact on human activities within the European Collaborative Action (ECA), e.g., Urban Air, Indoor Environment, and Human Exposure, as well as funded studies, EN standards, etc.); however, to date, there is still no integrated policy on indoor air quality in all of those indoor places.

The last, but not the least, the **Ambient Air Quality Directives**. In its work programme for 2022, the European Commission announced that it would propose a revision of the EU Ambient Air Quality Directives (Directives 2004/107/EC and 2008/50/EC).

Under the European Green Deal, the EU has set itself the objective of reducing air, water and soil pollution to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems and respecting the boundaries the planet can cope with by 2050 ('EU's zero pollution ambition'). Under the zero-pollution action plan for air, water and soil, tabled on 12 May 2021, the Commission committed to revise the EU's air quality standards to align them more closely with the World Health Organization (WHO) global air quality guidelines. The WHO updated, and tightened, its guidelines in September 2021.

On 26 October 2022, the Commission tabled its proposal for a revision, merging the two EU Ambient Air Quality Directives into a single directive. While introducing a zero-pollution objective for air, to be achieved by 2050, the proposed directive would set interim 2030 EU air quality standards that are closer to WHO guidelines. For instance, the annual limit value for PM 2.5 would be reduced from 25 µg/m³ to 10 µg/m³ in 2030 (WHO guideline is 5 µg/m³). By 31 December 2028 (and every 5 years thereafter), the Commission would assess whether EU standards are still appropriate and whether additional air pollutants have to be covered. The review would evaluate the need to revise the directive to ensure alignment with WHO guidelines and the latest scientific information. The proposal would establish a right for people to be compensated where damage to their health has occurred wholly or partially as a result of a violation of EU air quality rules.

4. Climate classification and building typologies

4.1 Cities and building typologies selection

The selection of the cities to characterize the different climate zones and building typologies was done in the framework of WP1 with the involvement of the consortium partners. The cities were selected in order to cover the five climate zones according to the classification done by ECOFYS according to the report “*Towards nearly zero-energy buildings*” [27].

The selection of the cities was also based on the results of other European projects where specific climate zones were taken as reference as for benchmarking new concepts to allow the BIOBUILD to have an easier and fair comparison with other technologies.

Therefore, to characterize climates, from northern Europe to southern Europe the following cities were selected:

- Athens (Greece)
- Madrid (Spain)
- Stockholm (Sweden)
- Stuttgart (Germany)
- Budapest (Hungary)

Regarding the building typologies, BIOBUILD technologies can be mainly applied to residential buildings. The residential building typologies characterized are correspond to the categories identified in TABULA/EPISCOPE data which includes:

- Single family house
- Terrace house
- Multifamily house
- Apartment block

The BIOBUILD solution can be also applied to non-residential buildings. In this case *offices* were selected as building typology, being the type with similar comfort and energy needs of residential buildings. In this report, a review of data available from the literature and various European projects was conducted to classify the construction typologies in terms of age, main building characteristics, and specific energy consumption for heating and cooling. However, to characterize the structure and the different typologies of commercial/non-residential buildings (i.e., offices), finding data is complex, since there is not a methodical way to collect data, especially for old buildings which makes poor data available.

4.2 Climate zones characterization

This section characterizes the different climates selected in the previous section. The meteorological parameters necessary to describe climate characterization for each location includes:

- Maximum ambient temperature
- Mean ambient temperature
- Minimum ambient temperature
- Relative humidity (RH)

To describe heating and cooling requirements with the help of mean daily temperature method, the values of heating degree days (HDDs) and cooling degree days (CDDs) were calculated based on the difference between the mean ambient temperature and base temperature.

Whereas base temperature is a fixed value that depends on the factors associated with building and surrounding environment. In the next sections, the value of HDDs and CDDs were calculated with a base temperature of

30(96)

15°C and 18.3°C for the HDD and CDD respectively and then compared with literature. The TRNSYS and Meteonorm database were used for climate data collection for above mentioned five cities. Meteonorm library provides different metrological properties collected experimentally from various stations in different time resolution in the world. Some properties that were not available were calculated based on interpolation method.

4.2.1 Zone 1: Athens

Athens is the capital city of Greece. It is located most south-eastern part of Europe. The climate of Greece is characterized by various climate typologies as shown in Figure 8, however Athens is characterized by Mediterranean climate. Athens, enjoys a mild wet winter in the southern downlands and hot dry summer. The HDDs and the CDDs of Athens [28] are:

- HDDs (base temperature 15°C): 876
- CDDs (base temperature 18.3°C): 1020

Figure 8. Köppen-Geiger climate classification in Greece.

The weather characteristics for Athens is shown in a Table 8 for each month of the year. According to annual temperature data, the coldest months of the year for Athens are January, February and December. The average temperature in winter is slightly lower than 10°C; however, this value is still higher than the continental Europe. Indeed, in the coldest month, the maximum temperature can reach 18°C with a minimum temperature of 0°C. June and August were the warmest months of the year with a maximum temperature of 37.9°C and an average temperature of 27°C in July. Summer months were characterized by a dry climate with a relative humidity of around 50% that increases in the winter to 85%.

Table 8 – Athens climate data from TRNSYS, Meteonorm [29], [30].

Month	T_{mean} [°C]	T_{min} [°C]	T_{max} [°C]	RH [%]
Jan	9.15	0.00	17.50	66.00
Feb	9.69	0.80	19.20	70.00
March	11.77	2.30	23.00	56.00
April	15.30	5.30	26.20	74.50
May	20.24	9.10	32.40	58.00
June	24.27	14.50	34.40	54.00
July	27.04	17.60	37.90	44.50
Aug	26.67	17.60	36.30	45.00

Sept	22.97	14.40	33.20	55.00
Oct	18.26	8.70	28.30	62.50
Nov	14.18	5.10	24.60	75.50
Dec	9.15	0.00	17.50	85.00

4.2.2 Zone 2: Madrid

Madrid is one of the largest cities in Spain and the capital of the country. Madrid is located over 600 m above sea level and is one of the sunniest cities in Europe. According to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification [31] for Spain, Madrid is located in the part of Spain characterized by a Mediterranean climate (Figure 2) with a hot, dry summer and a mild winter.

The HDDs and the CDDs of Madrid are [31]:

- HDDs (base temperature 15°C): 1860
- CDDs (base temperature 18.3°C): 596

Table 9 shows the weather characteristics of Madrid for each month of the year. The coldest months of the year were January and December. The average temperature in winter was lower than the one in Athens reaching a minimum of -4.6°C with an average temperature of 5.4°C.

Figure 9. Köppen-Geiger climate classification in Spain [31].

Table 9 – Madrid climate data from TRNSYS, Meteonorm [29], [30].

Month	Tmean [°C]	Tmin [°C]	Tmax [°C]	RH [%]
Jan	5.44	-4.60	15.30	68.00
Feb	6.99	-3.80	19.40	62.00
March	9.31	-2.80	21.90	51.50
April	11.44	-2.10	23.90	87.00
May	15.56	3.10	29.20	75.00
June	20.15	5.80	33.50	56.50
July	24.34	9.00	36.80	53.00
Aug	23.87	9.40	35.60	47.00
Sept	20.03	7.20	33.40	48.00
Oct	14.50	2.70	26.80	57.00
Nov	8.81	-3.30	21.10	85.00
Dec	5.44	-4.60	15.30	85.50

4.2.3 Zone 3: Stockholm

Stockholm is the most populated city of Sweden, located at the intersection of Baltic Sea and lake Malaren. Approximately 1.6 million people live in urban area and 2.4 million people live in metropolitan area. The city was selected for the characterization of Nordic climate. According to Köppen-Geiger classification, Stockholm climate is characterized as temperate oceanic climate or subtropical highland climate as shown in Figure 10. Stockholm has a humid continental, cold, no dry season, warm summer climate classified as dfb.

Figure 10. Köppen-Geiger climate classification in Sweden [28], [31].

The mean annual temperature of Stockholm is around 7°C which is 1% higher than the Sweden. From the data given in Table 10, the coldest month in Stockholm is February with minimum temperature of -5.3°C and least mean temperature -3°C. Meanwhile in the summer, July is the hottest month in Stockholm. The value of average temperature is 17.2°C and maximum temperature for the month of July is 21.9°C. Relative humidity decreases as the summer arrives and goes up to 85% in December in winters.

Table 10 – Stockholm climate data from TRNSYS, Meeonorm [29].

Month	T_{mean} [°C]	T_{min} [°C]	T_{max} [°C]	RH [%]
Jan	-2.8	-5	-0.7	85
Feb	-3	-5.3	-0.6	81
March	0.1	-2.7	3	78
April	4.6	1.1	8.6	72
May	10.7	6.3	15.7	65
June	15.6	11.3	20.7	66
July	17.2	13.4	21.9	72
Aug	16.2	12.7	20.4	75
Sept	11.9	9	15.1	81
Oct	7.5	5.3	9.9	84
Nov	2.6	0.7	4.5	88
Dec	-1	-3.2	1.1	87

4.2.4 Zone 4: Stuttgart

Stuttgart is the capital city of German state Baden-Wurtemberg and is located on a Neckar River in a fertile valley. It has an oceanic climate (cfb). The weather in Stuttgart is characterized as warm in summer with average high as 25°C and chilly in winter with daily mean temperature just above freezing. Stuttgart experiences 1807 hours of sunshine on average per year with an average annual temperature of 9°C. The mean annual precipitation in Stuttgart is measured around 25.58 inches or 646.7 mm. Köppen-Geiger climate classification in Germany is shown in the Figure 11.

Figure 11. Köppen-Geiger climate classification in Germany [31].

From the weather characterization data of Stuttgart city provided in Table 11 minimum temperature recorded is -3°C in the month of January. The mean temperature for January and February is -3°C and -2°C respectively hence these months are the coldest months of the city. In the summer, July and August are the hottest months with mean temperature of 19°C and the maximum temperature recorded is 24°C for each month. The relative humidity values are low in summer and high in winters for the Stuttgart city.

Table 11 – Stuttgart climate data from TRNSYS, Meteonorm [29].

Month	T_{mean} [°C]	T_{min} [°C]	T_{max} [°C]	RH [%]
Jan	0	-3	3	77
Feb	1.5	-2	5	76
March	5.5	1	10	68
April	9.5	5	14	64
May	13.5	8	19	63
June	17	12	22	67
July	19	14	24	66
Aug	18.5	13	24	69
Sept	15	10	20	73
Oct	10	6	14	77
Nov	5	2	8	79
Dec	1	-2	4	80

4.2.5 Zone 5: Budapest

Budapest is the capital city of Hungary, and the second largest city on the Danube river. The city is built on the heights of terraces and hills on the west and east riversides. Budapest has a humid temperate climate with warm to hot summers and chilly winters (cfa). The city receives a little sunshine in winters (November until early March). There is rapid increase in temperature in the months of April and May. Budapest experiences long summer from May to mid-September usually warm or very warm. The autumn in Budapest is usually characterized by pleasant weather with moderate temperature. The mean annual precipitation in Budapest is

measured around 23.5 inches or 596.9 mm. Köppen-Geiger climate classification in Hungary is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Köppen-Geiger climate classification in Hungary [31].

The Budapest climate data is provided in Table 12. From the table, the month of January is the coldest month with mean temperature of -0.5°C. The minimum and maximum temperature recorded for this month is -2.7°C and 2°C respectively. July and August, are the hottest months in Budapest. The maximum temperature measured is 27.1°C and 26.7°C in July and August respectively. The value of relative humidity in the summer is around 60% and in the winter relative humidity recorded is around 80%.

Table 12 – Budapest climate data from TRNSYS, Meteonorm [29].

Month	T_{mean} [°C]	T_{min} [°C]	T_{max} [°C]	RH [%]
Jan	-0.5	-2.7	2	79
Feb	2	-0.5	5.1	74
March	6.4	2.9	10.8	66
April	11.8	7.4	16.9	59
May	16.6	11.8	22	61
June	19.7	14.9	25	61
July	21.5	16.4	27.1	59
Aug	20.9	16	26.7	61
Sept	16.9	12.6	22.6	67
Oct	11.5	7.8	16.4	72
Nov	5.7	3.3	8.5	78
Dec	1.5	-0.5	3.8	80

4.3 Building typology characterization

In this section, only new buildings typologies were considered for energy demand and consumption. Two main categories of building typology were identified and characterized that include:

- Residential buildings
- Commercial buildings (offices)

Residential buildings mainly consist of single-family houses (SFH), multifamily houses (MFH), terrace houses (TH) and apartment blocks (AB). These building typologies were characterized for each location as a boundary condition as shown in Figure 13. In order to classify the construction typology in terms of age, main buildings characteristics and specific energy consumption for heating and cooling, a review of data was conducted from

the literature and various European projects. The main source of database used for the characterization of residential buildings were ENTRANZE [32], TABULA [33], INSPIRE [34]. These EU co-funded projects elaborate a building stock to access age, size and represents the several building typologies for the European countries. ENTRANZE [32] focuses on the building stock policy making by providing database, data analysis of energy demand and consumption guidelines to achieve net zero energy buildings. The literature review was conducted for chosen five cities that represent the different climate zones of Europe, particularly Nordic, continental, and southern zone. On the other hand, the commercial/non-residential buildings consist of variety of structures across the Europe depending on weather and luxuries. Similarly for the energy demand and consumption data in this building typology depends on several factors like weather, events and human behaviour. In May 2010 the European parliament and the council adopted a recast of the EU energy performance of buildings directive (Directive 2010/31/EU) with the aim to strengthen the energy performance requirements and to clarify some points from the 2002 directive it replaced. To characterize commercial building typologies precisely, only new and recent buildings are considered.

Figure 13. Building typologies in Europe [36].

4.1.1 Zone 1: Greece

4.1.1.1 Greek building stock

Greece is included in the Mediterranean climate region. Construction type in Greece is mainly connected to location. Mid-rise residential buildings are mainly found in cities and large towns and the construction method is reinforced concrete. In rural areas buildings are typically low-rise and single-family houses. These are usually constructed from load-bearing masonry or blockwork. The number of dwellings is 3.85 million and the proportion of the population living in SFHs and MFHs is 40.3% and 59.7% respectively ([35]). ENTRANZE [6] has given the number of SFH dwellings as 1.56 million and the number of MFH dwellings as 2.29 million. BPIE gives the total residential floor area in Greece as 250.9 Mm² with a split between SFHs and MFHs of 222 Mm² and 29 Mm² respectively. The percentage of residential and service buildings per subsectors in Greece are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. The residential and service buildings per subsectors in Greece [36].

4.1.1.2 Building energy consumption for heating and cooling

The development of final energy consumption for space heating in kWh/m² y before 1945 to post 2010 is shown in Figure 15. The energy consumption in residential buildings was about 160 kWh/m² year for specific final energy consumption for space heating and domestic heating water (DHW). There was a slight increase in energy consumption regarding buildings of 1980s. However, the rate of energy consumption drops to about 153 kWh/m² year in buildings erected between years 2000-2010. In contrast, the energy consumption trends in service sectors in Greece increased from 106 kWh/m² year to around 160 kWh/m² year.

Figure 15. Specific final energy consumption in space heating and DHW for building sectors in Greece [36].

The specific final energy consumption for space cooling in services sectors erected before 1945 is about 34 kWh/m² y whereas in residential buildings it is about 36 kWh/m² year. In Figure 16, the energy trends for space cooling remains the same with slight reduction in consumption in both sectors.

Figure 16. Specific final energy consumption in space cooling for building sectors in Greece [36].

4.1.1.3 Construction characterization

The information details regarding the thermal transmittance values (W/m²·K) of construction materials for Greece is given in Table 13. The construction typology for SFHs, MFHs, apartment blocks, and offices with thermal transmittance values and construction elements are described in detail for Greece. The data is for three different construction period from 1960-1980, 1981-2000 and 2001-2016.

Table 13 – Construction materials, construction methodology – service sector (Greece) [33], [36].

Year	Building typology		Single family house	Terrace house	Multifamily house	Apartment block	Offices
1960-1980	Roof	U value [W/m ² ·K]	3.05	N.a	3.05	N.a	3.1
		Material	Conventional flat roof	N.a	Conventional flat roof	N.a	Conventional flat roof
	Wall	U value [W/m ² ·K]	0.95	N.a	2.2	N.a	2.1
		Material	Double brickwork 10cm - plastered	N.a	Double brickwork 10 cm -plastered on both sides	N.a	Double brickwork 10 cm - plastered
	Floor	U value [W/m ² ·K]	3.1	N.a	3.1	N.a	2.8
		Material	Slab on grade	N.a	Slab on grade	N.a	Concrete slab
	Window	U value [W/m ² ·K]	3.1	N.a	4.7	N.a	5.1
		Material	Single glazed, wooden or synthetic frame	N.a	Single glazed, wooden or synthetic frame	N.a	Single glazed, wooden or synthetic frame
1981-2000	Roof	U value [W/m ² ·K]	3.05	N.a	3.05	N.a	2.8

		Material	Conventional flat roof	N.a	Conventional flat roof	N.a	Conventional flat roof	
	Wall	U value [W/m ² ·K]	0.85	N.a	2.51	N.a	0.8	
		Material	Double brickwork 10cm un-plastered on one or both sides - 3cm insulation	N.a	Double brickwork 10 cm with slightly ventilated air layer un-plastered on one side	N.a	Double brickwork 10 cm with slightly ventilated air layer un-plastered on one side	
	Floor	U value [W/m ² ·K]	2.75	N.a	3.1	N.a	0.9	
		Material	Pilotis	N.a	Slab on grade	N.a	Concrete slab	
	Window	U value [W/m ² ·K]	6.1	N.a	6.1	N.a	4.7	
		Material	Single glazed, metal frame	N.a	Single glazed, metal frame	N.a	Single glazed, metal frame	
	2001-2016	Roof	U value [W/m ² ·K]	0.5	N.a	0.5	N.a	0.4
			Material	Conventional flat roof - 6cm insulation	N.a	Conventional flat roof - 6cm insulation	N.a	Conventional flat roof – 6 cm insulation
		Wall	U value [W/m ² ·K]	0.6	N.a	0.6	N.a	0.7
Material			Double brickwork 10cm - plastered on both sides- 5cm insulation	N.a	Double brickwork 10cm - plastered on both sides- 5cm insulation	N.a	Double brickwork 10 cm - plastered on both sides- 5cm insulation	
Floor		U value [W/m ² ·K]	1.2	N.a	0.5	N.a	0.7	
		Material	Slab on grade, 3 cm insulation	N.a	Pilotis, 6 cm insulation	N.a	Flooring on the ground	
Window		U value [W/m ² ·K]	3.2	N.a	3.2	N.a	1.8	
		Material	Double glazed low-e, synthetic frame, according to KENAK (zone A)	N.a	Double glazed low-e, synthetic frame, according to KENAK (zone A)	N.a	Double glazed low-e, synthetic frame	

4.1.2 Zone 2: Spain

In Spain, buildings absorb 29.5% of final energy consumption, slightly below the EU, due to a milder climate. New buildings that have very high-energy performance will account for only 10% of the building stock in 2050. Currently, the housing stock in Spain amounts to 25.7 million (ministry of transport, mobility and urban agenda (MITMA)), 74.6% correspond to primary residences and mostly of a multifamily type (68%). The housing stock for non-residential use is close to 2 million properties according to the statistics of the real estate cadastre. In the field of energy retrofitting of buildings, Spain has a similar typology of measures to that of other EU countries, with two prevailing types. The regulatory measures include law 8/2013, of 26 June, on urban rehabilitation, regeneration and renewal; royal decree 235/2013, of 5 April, approving the energy certification of buildings; royal decree 238/2013, of 5 April, concerning the regulations on thermal installations of buildings (RITE); and royal decree 732/2019, of 20 December, amending the technical building code.

4.1.2.1 Spanish building stock

Figure 17 shows the breakdown of buildings typologies in residential and service sectors. The residential buildings mainly consist of single-family house (SFHs) by 2-3 floors, 4-8 floors in multifamily houses (MFHs) and more than 4 floors in apartment blocks (ABs). It is clear from the data that 69% widespread buildings are occupied by single family houses and terrace houses, remaining 31% for MFHs and ABs.

Figure 17. The residential and service subsectors in Spain [36].

4.1.2.2 Building energy consumption for heating and cooling

The energy consumption in buildings sectors remains almost the same from 1945 to 1969. However, there is decrease in energy consumption trends in both building typologies (residential and service sectors) for space heating and domestic water heating till post 2010 as shown in Figure 18, whereas the energy consumption for space cooling nearly remains the same for residential sectors as visualized in Figure 19.

Figure 18. Specific final energy consumption in space heating and DHW for building sectors in Spain [36].

Figure 19. Specific final energy consumption in space cooling for building sectors in Spain [36].

4.1.2.3 Construction characterization

The information details regarding construction material properties are provided in Table 14. The construction typology for SFHs, MFHs, apartment blocks and offices with thermal transmittance values and construction elements are described in detail for Spain. The data is for three different construction period from 1960-1979, 1980-2006 and 2007-2017. The insulation present in single family and multifamily houses was introduced after 1980. Concrete slabs are the most widespread technology for floors in Spanish houses.

Table 14 – Construction materials, construction methodology-service sector (Spain) [33], [36].

Typology			Single family house	Terrace house	Multifamily house	Apartment block	Offices
1960-1979	Roof	U value [W/m².K]	4.17	1.67	1.61	1.92	1.92

		Material	Ventilated pitched roof wooden frame and suspended ceiling	Ventilated Pitched roof with concrete	Ventilated flat roof with concrete horizontal framework	Flat roof: one-way framework with pre-stressed joint	Flat roof: one-way framework with pre-stressed joint	
	Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]	1.33	1.33	1.64	1.33	1.33	
		Material	Cavity wall: brick, air cavity	Cavity wall	Cavity wall: brick, air cavity	Cavity wall: brick, air cavity	Cavity wall: brick, air cavity	
	Floor	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.85	0.85	0.71	1.13	0.71	
		Material	Flooring on ground	Flooring on ground	One-way framework with pre-stressed joint	One-way framework with pre-stressed joint	One-way framework with pre-stressed joint	
	Window	U value [W/m ² .K]	4.59	5.7	5.7	5.7	5.7	
		Material	Metal frame, single glazed, no thermal break	Metal frame, single glazed	Metal frame, single glazed, no thermal break	Metal frame, single glazed, no thermal break	Metal frame, single glazed, no thermal break	
1980-2006	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.61	1.92	0.56	0.61	0.56	
		Material	Flat roof: one-way framework with pre-stressed joint	Flat roof: one-way framework with pre-stressed joint	Ventilated flat roof with concrete horizontal framework	Flat roof: one-way framework with pre-stressed joint	Ventilated flat roof with concrete horizontal framework	
		Wall	U value W/m ² .K	0.6	0.72	0.6	0.6	0.6
			Material	Cavity wall with insulation inside the cavity	Cavity wall with insulation inside the cavity	Cavity wall with insulation inside the cavity	Cavity wall with insulation inside the cavity	Cavity wall with insulation inside the cavity
		Floor	U value W/m ² .K	0.85	1.31	1.39	1.31	1.39
			Material	Flooring on the ground	One-way framework with pre-stressed joint	One-way framework, wooden joints	One-way framework, wooden joints	One-way framework, wooden joints
		Window	U value [W/m ² .K]	3.09	3.09	N.a	3.37	3.09
			Material	PVC frame, double glazed	PVC frame, double glazed	N.a	Metal frame, single glaze	Metal frame, single glaze
2007-2016	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.48	0.42	0.45	0.48	0.45	

		Material	Flat roof: one-way framework with pre-stressed joint				
Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]		0.48	0.48	0.52	0.48	0.52
	Material		Cavity wall	Cavity wall	Brick wall	Cavity wall	Brick wall
Floor	U value [W/m ² .K]		1.31	0.44	0.56	0.71	0.56
	Material		One-way framework with pre-stressed joint				
Window	U value [W/m ² .K]		3.09	2.92	3.37	3.37	3.37
	Material		PVC frame, double glazed	Metal frame, single glazed, thermal break	Metal frame, single glazed, no thermal break	Metal frame, single glazed, no thermal break	Metal frame, single glazed, no thermal break

4.1.3 Zone 3: Sweden

In contrast to other member states, the Swedish EPCs are (partly) based on the measured energy use of the building, which is used as the input data for issuing the EPC for new buildings. Energy use has to be measured during a period of 12 consecutive months and entered into the database by an independent certified energy expert. The energy use is then corrected for the climate variability by using a reference year. The energy use is also 'normalised', correcting for user-influence on energy consumption – for example, if the indoor temperature is different from the average indoor temperature of 22°C, or occupants use more domestic hot water than expected. The corrected value determines the energy class level of the EPC.

4.1.3.1 Swedish building stock

Figure 20 shows the results that were obtained from the building stock analysis database regarding Sweden. This data is obtained from online data tool TABULA and ENTRANZE. The percentage of residential buildings subsectors and percentage of service buildings subsectors in Sweden is provided.

Figure 20. The residential and service buildings per subsectors in Sweden [36], [37].

4.1.3.2 Building energy consumption for heating and cooling

Figure 21 and Figure 22 describe the energy consumption trends in Sweden for space heating, domestic water heating and space cooling. Energy consumption decreases rapidly from 1945 to 1969 in buildings and then there is slight decrease in consumption until post 2010.

Figure 21. Specific final energy consumption in space heating and DHW for building sectors in Sweden [36].

Figure 22. Specific final energy consumption in space cooling for building sectors in Sweden [36].

4.1.3.3 Construction characterizations

The information details regarding construction are provided in Table 15. The construction typology for SFHs, MFHs, apartment blocks and offices with thermal transmittance values and construction elements are described in detail for Sweden. The data is for three different construction period from 1976-1985, 1986-1995 and 1996-2005. The insulation present in single family and multifamily houses was introduced after 1980. Concrete slabs are the most widespread technology for floors in Swedish houses throughout all periods without insulation. The impact of buildings factor elements on specific energy consumption is also detailed in Table 15. It shows the effect of thermal insulation materials and building elements on the heat flow and energy consumption variation during the years.

Table 15 – Construction materials, construction methodology-service sector (Sweden) [33], [36].

	Typology		Single family house	Terrace house	Multifamily house	Apartment block	Offices
1976-1985	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.15	N.a	0.17	N.a	0.18
		Material	Horizontal wind	N.a	Horizontal wind	N.a	Horizontal wind
	Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.21	N.a	0.33	N.a	0.22
		Material	Wall single family house	N.a	Wall multi-family house	N.a	Bricks wall
	Floor	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.27	N.a	0.27	N.a	0.3
		Material	Concrete slab	N.a	Concrete slab	N.a	Concrete slab
	Window	U value [W/m ² .K]	2.01	N.a	2.04	N.a	2.01
		Material	Window	N.a	Window	N.a	Window
1986-1995	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.12	N.a	0.15	N.a	0.15
		Material	Horizontal wind	N.a	Horizontal wind	N.a	Horizontal wind
	Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.17	N.a	0.22	N.a	0.2
		Material	Wall single family house	N.a	Wall multi-family house	N.a	Bricks wall
	Floor	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.24	N.a	0.24	N.a	0.24
		Material	Concrete slab	N.a	Concrete slab	N.a	Concrete slab
	Window	U value [W/m ² .K]	1.94	N.a	2.08	N.a	3.09
		Material	Window	N.a	Window	N.a	Window
1996-2005	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.12	N.a	0.13	N.a	0.15
		Material	Horizontal wind	N.a	Horizontal wind	N.a	Horizontal wind
	Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.2	N.a	0.2	N.a	0.2

		Material	Wall single family house	N.a	Wall multi-family house	N.a	Brick wall
Floor		U value [W/m ² .K]	0.18	N.a	0.21	N.a	0.2
		Material	Concrete slab	N.a	Concrete slab	N.a	Concrete slab
Window		U value [W/m ² .K]	1.87	N.a	1.97	N.a	1.8
		Material	Window	N.a	Window	N.a	Window

4.1.4 Zone 4: Germany

Germany's individual renovation plan (Sanierungsfahrplan iSFP) was first launched in the federal state of Baden-Württemberg in 2015 and a newly developed "individueller sanierungsfahrplan" (iSFP) was launched at the national level in 2017. In Germany, EPCs are not considered reliable enough to stimulate renovation and are often viewed as an administrative obligation. On the other hand, there is a strong culture of on-site energy auditing, but the very detailed reports delivered to building owners (up to 150 pages) are often left unread and do not promote renovations. The iSFP has been designed as a user-friendly tool that includes both short- and long-term measures and suggests ways to avoid lock-in effects. As about 85% of the energy renovation measures funded in Germany concern only one building component, iSFP puts a strong focus on staged renovation and the interdependences between the stages. In Germany, the building owner is put at the very centre of the process, and the individual approach, including in-depth dialogues between the building owner and the energy auditors, is considered key for the instrument.

4.1.4.1 German building stock

Figure 23 visualizes the breakdown of different building types within the residential and service sectors. Residential buildings are usually characterized by 2-3 floors in SFHs, 4-8 floors in MFHs, and more than 4 floors in ABs. The graph shows that in the German residential sector, 71% of the buildings are characterized as SFHs. About 21% of the buildings are MFHs, the remaining 8% are referred to as ABs, respectively.

Figure 23. The residential and service buildings per subsectors in Germany [36].

4.1.4.2 Building energy consumption for heating and cooling

Figure 24 shows the development of the energy consumption for space heating and domestic water heating of the residential buildings and service sectors regarding buildings constructed before 1945 until post-2010. Buildings erected in 1945-1969 and to the late 1990s indicate the stable decrease in energy utilization. The

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consumption rate decreases from 280 kWh/m² year to 247 kWh/m² y regarding buildings erected in 1945-1969. The energy consumption of buildings erected in the 1980s and 1990s indicate 181 and 131 kWh/m² accordingly. In the residential sector of Germany (Figure 25), the trend of energy consumption for cooling shows that the buildings constructed before 1945 consume about 12 kWh/m² y. The consumption rate increases to almost 19 kWh/m² y regarding buildings erected between 1945 and 1969. The trend of energy consumption is then decreasing to 12 kWh/m² y regarding buildings constructed in the 1970s. Buildings erected in the 1980s and 1990s indicate relatively the same value of about 10 kWh/m² y.

Figure 24. Specific final energy consumption [kWh/m² y] in space heating and domestic heat water for building sectors in Germany [36].

Figure 25. Specific final energy consumption [kWh/m² y] in space cooling for building sectors in Germany [36].

4.1.4.3 Construction characterizations

The information details regarding construction are provided in Table 16. The construction typology for SFHs, MFHs, apartment blocks and offices with thermal transmittance values and construction elements are described in detail for Germany. The data is for three different construction period from 2002-09, 2010-15 and 2016-present. The flat roof is most popular concerning multifamily houses erected from 1945 to 1970s. A flat roof is also present in SFHs erected in the 1970s with the presence of insulation. Tilted roofs are primarily constructed in SFHs, and historical buildings erected before 1945.

Table 16 – Construction materials, construction methodology-service sector (Germany) [33][36].

Typology		Single family house	Terrace house	Multifamily house	Apartment block*	Offices	
2002-2009	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.25	0.2	0.2	0.51	0.2
		Material	Tilted roof with 16 cm insulation	Tilted roof with 18 cm insulation	Tilted roof with 18 cm insulation	Concrete ceiling with 5 cm insulation	Concrete ceiling with 10 cm insulation
	Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.3	0.3	0.25	1.1	0.6
		Material	Two layers of brickwork with 10 cm insulation	Two layers of brickwork with 10 cm insulation	Masonry with 14 cm render insulation system	Concrete panels	Concrete panels
	Floor	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.28	0.28	0.32	0.77	0.51
		Material	Concrete ceiling with 10 cm insulation	Concrete ceiling with 10 cm insulation	Concrete ceiling with 10 cm insulation	Concrete ceiling with 2 cm insulation	Concrete ceiling with 6 cm insulation
	Window	U value [W/m ² .K]	1.4	1.3	1.4	3	1.4
		Material	Aluminium window with dual-pane low-e glazing	Wooden window with dual-pane low-e glazing	Plastic window with dual-pane low-e glazing	Plastic frame window with dual-pane glazing	Plastic window with dual-pane low-e glazing
2010-2015	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.51	0.3
		Material	Insulate cavity between rafters + add insulation layer, total insulation thickness 21 cm	Insulate cavity between rafters + add insulation layer, total insulation thickness 21 cm	18 cm insulation on ceiling + roofing	Concrete ceiling with 5 cm insulation	18 cm insulation on ceiling + roofing
	Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.28	0.28	0.28	1.1	0.4
		Material	12 cm of external insulation brickwork + plaster (external insulated)	12 cm of external insulation brickwork + plaster (external insulated)	12 cm of external insulation brickwork + plaster (external insulated)	Concrete panels	12 cm of external insulation brickwork + plaster (external insulated)

			render system)	render system)	render system)		render system)
	Floor	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.77	0.35
	Floor	Material	(Bottom) slab + 10 cm external insulation	(Bottom) slab + 10 cm external insulation	(Bottom) slab + 10 cm external insulation	Concrete ceiling with 2 cm insulation	(Bottom) slab + 10 cm external insulation
	Window	U value [W/m ² .K]	1.3	1.3	1.3	2.7	1.3
	Window	Material	Windows with double glazing, argon filled, low-E	Windows with double glazing, argon filled, low-E	Windows with double glazing, argon filled, low-E	Composite window with two single panes in wooden frames	Windows with double glazing, argon filled, low-E
2016-Present	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.15	0.13	0.25	0.43	0.25
		Material	Insulation between wood I-joists, total insulation thickness 27 cm	Insulation between wood I-joists, total insulation thickness 29 cm	Flat roof: one-way framework with pre-stressed joint	Concrete ceiling with 6 cm insulation	Flat roof: one-way framework with pre-stressed joint
	Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.17	0.16	0.29	0.9	0.32
		Material	20 cm of external insulation brickwork + plaster (external insulated render system)	22 cm of external insulation brickwork + plaster (external insulated render system)	11 cm of external insulation brickwork + plaster (external insulated render system)	Concrete panels	11 cm of external insulation brickwork + plaster (external insulated render system)
	Floor	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.17	0.16	0.29	0.65	0.3
		Material	(Bottom) slab + 20 cm external insulation	(Bottom) slab + 22 cm external insulation	(Bottom) slab + 12 cm external insulation	Concrete ceiling with 4 cm insulation	(Bottom) slab + 12 cm external insulation
	Window	U value [W/m ² .K]	1.1	1.1	1.1	3	1.2
		Material	Windows with triple glazing, argon filled, low-E	Windows with triple glazing, argon filled, low-E	Windows with triple glazing, argon filled, low-E	Plastic frame window with dual-pane glazing	Windows with triple glazing, argon filled, low-E

4.1.5 Zone 5: Hungary

The Hungarian regulations requirements of buildings have three levels:

1. The requirements are set for the maximum allowable thermal transmittance of the building elements;
2. The specific heat loss coefficient of the building;
3. The integrated energy performance of the building service systems.

4.1.5.1 Hungarian building stock

Figure 26 depicts the breakdown of different building typologies. The percentage of residential buildings subsectors and percentage of service buildings subsectors in Hungary is provided.

Figure 26. *The residential and service buildings per subsectors in Hungary [36].*

4.1.5.2 Building energy consumption for heating and cooling

In the residential sector of Hungary, buildings erected before 1945 consume around 289 kWh/m² y of specific final energy consumption (FEC) for space heating (SH) and (DHW). The rate then drops to approximately 257 kWh/m² y in the buildings constructed in 1945-1969. Buildings constructed in the 1970s consume about 222 kWh/m² y. The consumption rate keeps dropping regarding buildings that have been erected lately. For instance, buildings constructed between 1980-1989 show the value of specific FEC for SH and DHW for about 183 kWh/m² y. The consumption rate then falls to approximately 149 kWh/m² y regarding buildings erected in the 1990s. After that, the consumption rate drops slightly regarding buildings of the 2000s, with the value of about 138 kWh/m² y. Buildings constructed in the post-2010 period show the value of specific FEC for SH and DHW of about 112 kWh/m² y. Buildings constructed in the 1970s consume about 222 kWh/m² y as shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27. Specific final energy consumption in space heating and domestic water heating for building sectors in Hungary [36].

The trend of specific FEC for cooling (Figure 28) in the residential sector of Hungary shows different variations as it keeps fluctuating. Buildings erected before 1945 consume about 6 kWh/m² y. This is the lowest specific FEC for SC that is observed in the residential and service sectors. The rate increases to approximately 16 kWh/m² y regarding buildings erected in 1945-1969. The consumption rate drops to about 9 kWh/m² y in buildings constructed in the 1970s. Buildings erected in the 1980s show almost the same rate, which is approximately 10 kWh/m² y. Buildings constructed in the 1990s consume about 7 kWh/m² y, whereas approximately the same, i.e., 10 kWh/m² y of specific FEC, is consumed by buildings erected from 2000 till 2010.

Figure 28. Specific final energy consumption in space cooling for building sectors in Hungary [36].

4.1.5.3 Construction characterizations

The information details regarding construction materials for Hungary is given in Table 17. The construction typology for SFHs, MFHs, apartment blocks and offices with thermal transmittance values and construction elements are described in detail for Hungary. The data is for three different construction period from 1980-1989, 1990-2005 and 2006-present.

Table 17 – Construction materials, construction methodology-service sector (Hungary) [33], [36].

Typology		Single family house	Terrace house	Multifamily house	Apartment block	Offices		
1980-1989	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.36	N.a	0.36	0.44	1.2	
		Material	Pitched roof, insulated	N.a	Pitched roof, insulated	Reinforced concrete flat roof	Pitched roof, insulated	
	Wall	U value [W/m ² .K]	1.37	N.a	1.35	0.7	1.33	
		Material	B30 walling block wall	N.a	Solid brick wall 38cm	Reinforced concrete sandwich panel	Solid brick wall 38cm	
	Floor	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.7	N.a	0.71	0.48	0.71	
		Material	Basement slab, prefab	N.a	Reinforced concrete basement slab	Reinforced concrete basement slab	Reinforced concrete basement slab	
	Window	U value [W/m ² .K]	2.5	N.a	2.5	2.5	2.5	
		Material	Double-pane wooden casement window	N.a	Double-pane wooden casement window	Double-pane wooden casement window	Double-pane wooden casement window	
	1990-2005	Roof	U value [W/m ² .K]	0.25	N.a	0.36	N.a	0.56
			Material	Pitched roof, insulated	N.a	Pitched roof, insulated	N.a	Pitched roof, insulated
Wall		U value [W/m ² .K]	0.49	N.a	0.32	N.a	0.5	
		Material	Thermal ins. walling block 30cm; 0,49	N.a	Attic slab, reinforced concrete,	N.a	Attic slab, reinforced concrete,	
Floor		U value [W/m ² .K]	0.37	N.a	0.49	N.a	0.6	
		Material	Basement slab	N.a	Thermal ins. walling block 30cm;	N.a	Thermal ins. walling block 30cm	
Window		U value [W/m ² .K]	2	N.a	0.2	N.a	0.25	

		Material	Wooden window, double-glazed	N.a	Wooden window, double-glazed	N.a	Wooden window, double-glazed
2006- Present	Roof	U value [W/m ² ·K]	1.26	N.a	0.25	0.25	0.3
		Material	Attic slab, reinforced concrete,	N.a	Pitched roof, insulated	Pitched roof, insulated	Pitched roof, insulated
	Wall	U value [W/m ² ·K]	0.22	N.a	0.21	0.22	0.21
		Material	Thermal ins. walling block 30cm	N.a	Attic slab, reinforced concrete,	Thermal ins. walling block 30cm	Attic slab, reinforced concrete
	Floor	U value [W/m ² ·K]	0.44	N.a	0.22	0.22	0.3
		Material	Floor above ground, parquet	N.a	Thermal ins. walling block 30cm	Basement slab	Basement slab
	Window	U value [W/m ² ·K]	1.5	N.a	1.5	1.5	1.5
		Material	Window, double- glazed	N.a	Window, double-glazed	Window, double- glazed	Window, double- glazed

5. Existing standards and standardization activities landscape

5.1 Benefits of standards and standardisation for research and innovation and industry

Standards are documented agreements containing technical specifications or other precise criteria to be used consistently as rules, guidelines or definitions, to ensure that materials, products, processes and services are fit for their purpose. Standards provide people and organizations with a basis for mutual understanding, and are used as tools to facilitate communication, measurement, commerce and manufacturing. Standards are developed for safety and reliability reasons, where users perceive standardized products and services as more dependable – this in turn raises user's confidence, increases sales and the take-up of new technologies. Standards are developed as a collaborative process that includes manufacturers, users, consultants, governments and other interested parties. Standardization bodies seek to have all parties concerned at the table during the development of standards. When stakeholders are not represented during the development of the standard, the outcome may be less than optimal for stakeholders that use the standards. The development of standards takes up to several years. During this time, it is also possible that processes have evolved which makes the standard already outdated once it is published. To tackle this issue a systematic review of standards is therefore in place.

Standards can support R & I, they promote the adoption of new technologies in several ways. Importantly, they can codify and spread state-of-the-art research in various areas and bridge the gap between research and end products or services. When knowledge of innovations is codified in standards, it is accessible to everybody, so firms, universities and research organisations can use it to perform research, generate new ideas and adopt innovations.

Moreover, standards are commonly used as inputs to research but can also be an output of research activities. Multiple studies have explored the role of standards in supporting and driving R & I, and these have identified various benefits flowing from the integration of standardisation within research.

Significantly, standards improve the research process by providing common terminologies, harmonised methodologies and comparability between research activities. They can also enhance the marketability of R & I results. Standards also contribute to bridging the gap between research and the market by:

- fostering dissemination and long-term exploitation of research results;
- accelerating access to the European market for new products, methods and services;
- facilitating networking between stakeholders in the R & I system.

Knowledge and technology transfer is generally described as the transfer of know-how, technical knowledge or technology from one organisational environment to another, with many variations depending on the research discipline and purpose. Knowledge and technology transfer typically occurs between universities, research institutions and companies – but also within companies. However, standardisation has only recently been considered an option for university – industry relations. In contrast, a decade ago, it was still ignored, although the first studies, funded through EU framework programmes, were published 15 years ago.

Within internal R & I process, companies perceive standardisation as a synchronised development tool, for example in biotechnology that involves and brings together all functional units involved in the innovation process. Standardisation, therefore, forms a platform for knowledge and technology transfer during the process of developing new products and makes it easier to scale up complex product prototypes and transfer them to industrial-scale production. Standards promote the exchange of knowledge and the coordination of research and development (R & D) efforts and enable the (organisational) discrepancies between laboratories and production processes to be overcome. By harmonising terminology in the standardisation process and standards themselves, as is generally the case in knowledge transfer activities, good communication between the front end (the practical application) and the back end (the scientific work behind it) is crucial. An open corporate culture and the participation of different disciplines are necessary for this exchange to happen [21].

Since standardisation committees include representatives from all interest groups, scientists from applied research can come into contact with companies. Their joint work in standardisation creates mutual trust and thus increases the likelihood that companies and research institutions will network sustainably and work on common issues, for example in collaborative and contract research.

Furthermore, organisations can gain new impetus for technology developments through standardisation. Technologies do not necessarily have to be developed from scratch, but protected knowledge and technologies can be acquired, for example, through licences for standard-essential patents. Furthermore, standards represent the state of the art in a technology area and help companies establish dominant designs.

It must be taken in consideration that once technologies have been integrated into standards, they can no longer be patented. Accordingly, the strategic prevention of patents as a particular case can motivate companies to engage in standardisation activities. Another driver is the broader diffusion of research results. The availability, accessibility and applicability of standards enables the widespread dissemination of the knowledge generated.

5.2 Current landscape in European and international standardization

A balance between energy, performance, and cost efficiency are critical issues in all engineering fields. Nearly 40% of energy consumption and 36% of greenhouse gas emissions are caused by residential and commercial buildings. Therefore, there are initiatives to reduce these emissions and energy consumption while increasing the sustainability of the built environment through the concept of near-zero energy (NZE) buildings. One of the key aspects of NZE buildings is the use of sustainable and energy-efficient materials for construction. In response to this challenge, ongoing researches direction is aimed at developing new eco-friendly, non-structural multipurpose materials with sound- or thermal-insulating properties. In this context, all-natural composite materials have emerged as a promising alternative to synthetic polymer composites for various applications, including sound insulation and non-structural panels.

The aim of BIOBUILD project is to develop and demonstrate fully bio-based building materials with thermal storage function that can replace high environmental footprint products.

For the bio-based industry, the European Commission identified that standards are needed to promote the uptake of its products by consumers, facilitate the functioning of the Single Market, and enable public authorities to implement 'green procurement' policies. Mandated by the European Commission, the CEN/TC 411 'Bio-based products' developed standards that cover horizontal aspects of bio-based products. These standards play a crucial role in supporting the growth of the bio-based products market. They can help to increase market transparency by providing common reference methods and requirements that enable the verification of claims and certification regarding the bio-based content, bio-degradability or environmental sustainability of different products. Certification is a procedure by which a third party gives written assurance that a product, process or service is in conformity with certain standards. Over the last years many certificates have been developed by NGOs, authorities or certification bodies to help consumers, manufacturers, distributors and traders choose the right products for their purpose and to provide for conformance testing (more about testing and certification of bio-based building materials will be develop in D1.2 and D1.3). Among others, certificates help to demonstrate the sustainability of biomass, the bio-based content of a product or the end-of-life options. As a result, many certification schemes are available in the market.

The energy consumption of buildings depends significantly on the criteria used for the indoor environment, which also affect the health, productivity and comfort of the occupants. The indoor environment is mentioned several times in the EPBD (Energy Performance of Buildings Directive), aspects of thermal comfort related to low temperature or draught are often improved through measures that are primarily addressed at improving the energy performance of a building. Today still, between 50 and 125 million Europeans suffer from cold in winter.

The European Standards specifies the indoor environmental parameters that have an impact on the energy performance of buildings. The EN 16798-1:2019 (EN 16798 series have 15 standards in the present) standard specifies how to establish indoor environmental input parameters for building system design and energy

performance calculations, methods for long-term evaluation of the indoor environment, displaying the indoor environment in existing buildings and criteria for measurements and monitoring. This standard is applicable to the following building types: single family houses, apartment buildings, offices, educational buildings, hospitals, hotels and restaurants, sports facilities, wholesale and retail trade service buildings. An example of recommended design values of the indoor temperature is presented in Table B.5 from Annex B of the document (reproduced below).

Table 18 – Temperature ranges for hourly calculation of cooling and heating energy in four categories of indoor environment.

Type of building or space	Category	Temperature range for heating seasons, °C Clothing approximately 1,0 clo	Temperature range for cooling seasons, °C Clothing approximately 0,5 clo
Residential buildings, living spaces (bed room's, kitchens, living rooms etc.) Sedentary activity ~1,2 met	I	21,0 – 25,0	23,5 - 25,5
	II	20,0–25,0	23,0 - 26,0
	III	18,0- 25,0	22,0 - 27,0
	IV	17,0–25,0	21,0 – 28,0
Residential buildings, other spaces (utility rooms, storages etc.) Standing-walking activity ~1,5 met	I	18,0–25,0	
	II	16,0–25,0	
	III	14,0–25,0	
Offices and spaces with similar activity (single offices, open plan offices, conference rooms, auditoria, cafeteria, restaurants, class rooms) Sedentary activity ~1,2 met	I	21,0 – 23,0	23,5 - 25,5
	II	20,0 – 24,0	23,0 - 26,0
	III	19,0 – 25,0	22,0 - 27,0
	IV	17,0–25,0	21,0 – 28,0
During the between heating and cooling seasons (with θ_{rm} between 10 and 15°C) temperature limits that lie in between the winter and summer values may be used. Air velocity is assumed < 0,1 m/s and RH~40% for heating season and 60% for cooling season.			

If we were to consider only this series of standards for our project, we would notice how important European and international standards are for the evaluation and selection of the best methods and tests for bio-construction materials.

Studies carried out in office buildings have shown that the requirements of the occupants in terms of the thermal environment can be different in buildings that have a mechanical cooling system and in buildings where the occupants, in order to influence the thermal environment, they only have the option of opening the windows. Therefore, the design criteria differ for these two types of office buildings: mechanically heated and mechanically cooled buildings and buildings without mechanical cooling (see definition in EN 16798-1 too). The decision regarding the approach used is taken by the client and his consultant, in the field of energy performance of the respective building. The consultant has the opportunity to demonstrate the difference between the two methods (acceptable indoor temperatures, energy consumption, etc.).

Thermal ambient criteria in heated and/or cooled buildings are based, in EN 16798-1, on thermal comfort indices PMV-PPD (predictable mean vote – predictable percentage of dissatisfied), with usual levels assumed activity

and usual clothing thermal insulation values (winter and summer), as described in detail in EN ISO 7730. By setting different criteria for PPD, different indoor ambience categories are established.

The PMV-PPD index takes into account the influence of six thermal parameters (clothing, activity, air temperature, average radiation temperature, air speed and humidity) and can be used directly as a criterion.

Local thermal discomfort criteria (EN 16798-1) such as air currents, radiation temperature asymmetry, vertical air temperature differences and floor temperatures also influence the design of buildings and technical systems and are recommended to be taken into account .

In order to identify the relevant European and International standards related to BIOBUILD project scope from first year of the project (WP1) The Romanian Standards Body (ASRO) and the Consortium partners performed a thoroughly research activity using the following means:

- The European and International Standardization Organizations platforms:
 - CEN <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>
 - CENELEC <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>
 - ISO <https://www.iso.org/home.html>
 - IEC <https://iec.ch/homepage>
- National Mirror Committees on bio building materials for identifying the potential homegrown standards relevant for BIOBUILD,
- Input of WP 1 partners according to their knowledge and experience.

Following the research activity a number of 111 European, International and National standards were identified (Annex 1 and Annex 2).

The general distribution of the identified standards is:

- 86 European standards, standardization documents and projects of standards
- 25 international standards and standardization documents

For the European standards the most relevant Technical Committees are:

- CEN/TC 175 Round and sawn timber
- CEN/TC 112 Wood-based panels
- CEN/TC 38 Durability of wood and wood-based products
- CEN/TC 411 Bio-based products
- CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products
- CEN/TC 127 Fire safety in buildings
- CEN/TC 134 Resilient, textile, laminate and modular mechanical locked floor coverings

At International level the following Technical Committees were identified:

- ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment
- ISO/TC 165 Timber structures
- ISO/TC 92 Fire safety
- ISO/TC 43 Acoustics
- ISO/TC 218 Timber
- ISO/TC 207 Environmental management

The number of standards identified from different domains (Technical Committees) is shown in the following figures:

Figure 29. Breakdown of ISO standards by fields (ISO TCs).

Figure 30. Breakdown of CEN standards by fields (CEN TCs).

During the implementation of BIOBUILD project some other standards may be added to the list.

Some of the limits and requirements of these standards have already been used in this report, but most of them will be used when developing the other two reports in WP1:

- Technical, market codes, and certification strategies;
- Definition and selection of KPIs.

For many years product standards have been developed that specify requirements to be fulfilled by a product or a group of products, to determine its fitness for purpose. Most of these standards have been developed when fossil-based products were still the “mainstream” products. Most of these standards are developed to evaluate the characteristics of materials to demonstrate this fitness whereas it would be more appropriate to evaluate the functionality of materials or products against the requirements of the application. For bio-based products to demonstrate their fitness for purpose they must comply with tests based upon these standards. This was the reason we selected its.

The building sector is a traditional sector when looking at materials. As bio-based materials do not have a track record as long as traditional fossil-based products, bio-based product developers are required to prove that these materials are functionally equivalent to traditional materials.

Certifying bodies that evaluate these materials use reference standards or (standard) test methods that are developed to evaluate the quality of fossil-based products. All those gaps in existing European standards will be identified and recommendations for the other activities in the BIOBUILD project will be provide in the next deliverable, *D1.2 - Technical, market codes, and certification strategies*.

6. Environmental benchmarks for buildings

6.1 LCA approaches

The idea of LCA was conceived in the 1960s when environmental degradation and in particular the limited access to resources started becoming a concern. LCA had its early roots in packaging studies and focused mainly on energy use and a few emissions, spurring a largely un-coordinated method development in the US and Northern Europe .

It might come as a surprise – but the first Life Cycle Assessment was conducted by Coca Cola in 1969!

The late 60's were a time of sustainable awakening: the oil crisis and concerns about population growth led to environmental movements in many countries. The study “The Limits of Growth” summarized that sentiment in 1972. Economic considerations, led Coca Cola to an internal study that can be considered as the foundation of today's LCA methodology.

The first studies were primarily carried out for companies, who used them internally and made little communication to stakeholders. After a silent period in the 1970s, the 1980s and 1990s saw an increase in methodological development and international collaboration and coordination in the scientific community and method development increasingly took place in universities.

In this first particular study, Coca Cola quantified the raw materials and fuels used, as well as the environmental impact of the manufacturing processes.

This methodology was known as Resource and Environmental Profile Analysis (REPA). The European equivalent was called an Ecobalance (The German name of Life Cycle Assessment, Ökobilanz, is directly derived from this term).

With the consolidation of the methodological basis, application of LCA widened to encompass a rapidly increasing range of products and systems with studies commissioned or performed by both industry and governments, and results were increasingly communicated through academic papers and industry and government reports. To this day, methodological development has continued, and increasing attention has been given to international scientific consensus building on central parts of the LCA methodology, and standardisation of LCA and related approaches.

The US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) published their LCA 101, a first document to support the upcoming methodology, in the 1980's.

The European commission followed in 1985 and issued the Liquid Food Container Directive in 1985.

In the late 80's, companies started using environmental footprints in their marketing claims. Since there was very little standardization, this quickly became an issue.

This is why in 1991, the USA denounced the use of LCA results until further standards were in place.

Sustainable development was developed its official definition in the Brundtland report 1987 to eliminate the negative consequences of rising only the quality of life for the present generation. It embraces the idea of having the ability to meet the current needs without threatening the future capability to satisfy their own needs. Based on the fact that we are rapidly depleting non-renewable resources; energy, and raw materials, the consciousness of sustainability has rapidly increased worldwide in the last decade. The awareness is with the target of avoiding the environmental impacts occurred by different types of human activities. Activities with harmful ecological effects vary from one industry to another. However, it is stated that the building industry is the most contributor to Green House Gases emissions (GHG).

The ACE sector (Architecture, Construction and Engineering) has intensive attention as the building industry robustly influences the environment. It is considered to have the largest share in the natural resources drain and the foremost reason for undesirable impacts such as air and water pollution, solid waste, deforestation, toxic wastes, health hazards, global warming, and other harmful effects.

GHG emissions impacts have the most consideration from researchers and policymakers, although it is just one of a wide range of impacts. So, it becomes clear that there is a need for a holistic perspective of materials to evaluate all the environmental impacts throughout its whole life cycle.

Thus, to evaluate a material's total impacts, all life cycle stages as shown in Figure 31) must be considered, from material extraction, manufacturing, construction, use, including operations, maintenance, demolition, and disposal. The main reason for considering all types of environmental issues is to avoid what is called “Burden Shifting”. It happens when the improvement in a specific stage of the material life cycle concerning one kind of environmental impact can lead unintentionally to a rise in the other types of impacts for the same stage or different life cycle stages.

In that context, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has been indicated to be an applicable emerging approach to evaluate products and materials concerning their environmental performance. LCA has undergone a robust development in approaches and applications since it was conceived in the 1960s. LCA promises to strengthen the architectural decision-making by investigating the environmental impact of buildings materials and concluding to techniques to decrease these impacts. Even though the LCA method provides a quantifiable measurement of environmental impact, awareness of the strength and weaknesses points of LCA is essentially required to ensure the ability to understand the LCA procedure.

From the early beginning to now, methodological development of (LCA) has still undergone with attention to the new approaches and tools to support the seamless procedure.

Figure 31. Life Cycle stages of a building with different approaches [22].

The LC allegory is driven from the biology field. In biology, the “LC” term refers to the organism constant sequence of changes from one initial form, as a gamete, to the development of the same form again for the cycle to be repetitive”.

In a simplified way, every material has its own lifetime process called the Life Cycle. It has been proven that a material's life cycle results in a wide range of environmental impacts. Therefore, the Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) concept refers to taking into consideration the upstream and downstream of the material in a holistic perspective.

Practically the ultimate target of LCT is to enhance the environmental and Socio-Economic performance throughout its life cycle. In detail, it aims to help companies and customers to be more aware of how their decisions impact the environment from a holistic perspective and make better alternative decisions to mitigate environmental impacts.

Throughout the years, LCA has had different attempts to be officially defined as a new approach. The first initial definition was introduced in 1990 by the SETAC workgroup as a comprehensive tool for assessing the environmental burdens related to a product, process, or activity by analysing the energy, materials used, and wastes generated. The assessment involves the product's whole life cycle from extraction of raw materials, manufacturing, transportation and distribution, use/reuse/maintenance, recycling to final disposal. Furthermore, ISO 14040 also defined LCA as a systematic approach for evaluating the inputs and outputs of materials and energy related to a process or product to analyse the potential environmental impacts caused throughout its life cycle.

LCA methodologies and international standardization

The number of seminars, guides, and handbooks in the 1990s reflected the outstanding global coordination activities growth. From 1991 to 1994, a cooperation amongst LCA specialists was established through the North American and European branches of the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC). This collaboration was resulted continual development and standardization of LCA framework and methodology. One of the most important outcomes of this coloration was the “Code of Practice”.

For a manufacturer, it is crucial to showcase the environmental impact of their products. For many manufacturers the problem can be define as: should I opt for a Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) or an Environmental Product Declaration (EPD)?

The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology has been developed by the European Commission as a tool for advancing various product sustainability initiatives of the European Commission. The PEF methodology refers to the standards: ISO 14040, ISO 14025, ISO 14067, and ISO 14020. The general purpose of PEF is to support European policy as a potential methodology for regulations. Its specified intended applications are to support in-house product sustainability analyses as well as B2B and B2C communication.

The EPD methodology has been developed by the CEN/TC 350 Sustainability of Construction works, which is a standardization group consisting of industry experts and other stakeholders (LCA consultants, government experts, NGOs, etc.) developing standards for the EU and global market. The EPD standard applies the ISO 14040 and 14025 and other standards. The general purpose of the EPD standard is to support B2B communication and regulations. The EPD data is also used for purpose of project-level life-cycle assessment of construction works under the related EN 15978 and other standards.

Moreover, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has been engaged in LCA since 1994. Parallel to the focus of the SETAC working group on improving and harmonizing methodologies, ISO took the formal mission of methods and procedures standardization. Despite the lack of standardized methods, the standard met industry requirements for using LCA for product development. Over the next seven years, four standards were released based on the standard development:

- a) principles and framework (ISO 14040) in 1997;
- b) goal and scope definition (ISO 14041) in 1998;
- c) life cycle impact assessment (ISO 14042) in 2000 and
- d) life cycle interpretation (ISO 14043) in 2000.

The ISO 14040 series standards, Life Cycle Assessment, address quantitative assessment methods for the assessment of the environmental aspects of a product or service in its entire life cycle stages. ISO 14040 is an overarching standard encompassing all four phases of LCA.

The ISO 14040:2006 - *Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework* (confirmed in 2022), covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies. It does not describe the LCA technique in detail, nor does it specify methodologies for the individual phases of the LCA.

The intended application of LCA or LCI results is considered during the goal and scope definition, but the application itself is outside the scope of this International Standard.

The document describes the principles and framework for life cycle assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase, the life cycle interpretation phase, reporting and critical review of the LCA, limitations of the LCA, the relationship between the LCA phases, and conditions for use of value choices and optional elements.

ISO 14040:2006 covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies. It does not describe the LCA technique in detail, nor does it specify methodologies for the individual phases of the LCA. Besides these pivotal events, there were several attempts to standardize the LCA methodology. For instance, the CML92 method created by the University of Leiden in the Netherlands, and the Eco-indicator method, the first endpoint assessment technique and still the furthestmost widely used in LCA.

Besides the standards/methodologies mentioned above should be remembered too:

- ISO 14067 on the carbon footprint of products - “specifies principles, requirements and guidelines for the quantification and reporting of the carbon footprint of a product”— that is, its impact on climate change. “Carbon offsetting and communication of CFP” are “outside the scope” of the standard.

The standard is consistent with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044. However, it also includes requirements on specific issues relevant to carbon footprinting, including land-use change, carbon uptake, biogenic carbon emissions, and soil carbon change.

- ISO 14020, ISO 14021, ISO 14024, ISO 14025, and ISO 14026 on environmental labels. These standards set out principles, requirements and guidelines for the development and use of environmental labels and declarations, as well as for the communication of footprint information.
- ILCD (EU) on life cycle assessment. The International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) handbook, which was developed by the European Commission Joint Research Centre, offers technical guidelines on conducting detailed LCA studies. It contains detailed descriptions and requirements in order to reduce flexibility in choices and to support the consistency of LCA results and quality assurance related to these. It is consistent with the ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards.
- EcoLeaf Environmental Labeling Program (Japan) – describes the methodology for assessing the environmental impact of products throughout their life cycle. This framework is a result of the integration of two different Japanese frameworks, EcoLeaf and Carbon Footprint of Products (CFP). The framework is consistent with the LCA ISO 14040 series.
- Carbon Footprint of Products and Environmental Product Declaration (Korea).

Carbon footprint of products (CFP) provides guidelines for assessing the life cycle carbon footprint of products. Three “phases” of carbon-footprint labelling are included: “Certification of Carbon Emissions (Phase 1), Certification of Low Carbon Products (Phase 2), and Certification of Carbon Neutral Products (Phase 3).” The environmental product declaration provides guidelines for assessing the life cycle environmental impacts of products in Korea.

6.2 Environmental constraints

Buildings and construction are closely linked to the economy, local employment and quality of life. Europe has many old cities with old buildings. Its building stock is also getting older and many old buildings are not built for efficient use of energy or a warmer climate.

Today, environmental issues are an extremely pressing topic in society with a huge push towards alternative energy solutions. Fortunately, there are various innovative and green options that construction companies can take to not only reduce environmental effects but save money as well. All it takes is a little thoughtful planning and any company should be on its way towards fostering smarter and sustainable building practices.

Buildings must be made to protect people from the effects of climate change, including extreme heat and cold spells, both of which entail higher energy consumption for heating or cooling. Energy inefficiency, energy poverty or the poor condition of buildings often affect some groups and communities more than others.

The construction process is a major user of the world's non-renewable energy sources. This produces a number of pollutants from synthetic chemicals as well as greenhouse gases including carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide. Some authors and studies argue that when these emissions are produced in excess, they contribute significantly to climate change.

The buildings and construction sector is by far the largest emitter of greenhouse gases, accounting for a staggering 37% of global emissions. The production and use of materials such as cement, steel, and aluminium have a significant carbon footprint.

Historically, much of the sector's progress has centered around reducing the "operational" carbon emissions of buildings – those emissions stemming from heating, cooling, and lighting. Projections suggest that these operational emissions will decrease from 75 to 50% of the sector's total emissions in the coming decades.

However, solutions to mitigate the buildings "embodied" carbon emissions – originating from the design, production, and deployment of materials such as cement, steel, and aluminium – have lagged. To effectively address this challenge, international action and collaboration must bring together all stakeholders from across the entire lifecycle of the buildings sector, both within informal and formal settings. That is also the intention of our project: to develop and demonstrate fully bio-based building materials with thermal storage function that can replace high environmental footprint products.

Environmental constraints could include:

- The use of sustainable or hazardous materials;
- Energy consumption and carbon emissions;
- Air, water or ground pollution or contamination;
- Waste and water management;
- Noise, vibration, and dust;
- Traffic and transport;
- Preservation of ecology;
- Resilience to climate change;
- Design for deconstruction and disposal.

These can often overlap with legal constraints, but additional requirements may be set out in EU environmental policies.

At EU level, almost 75% of the building stock is currently energy inefficient and more than 85% of today's buildings are likely to still be in use in 2050. Energy renovation of buildings is ongoing but at a very slow rate.

The EU's renovation wave will play a key role in massively upgrading existing buildings in Europe. It will help make them more energy efficient and adapted to climate change. This will be an important element in achieving a climate-neutral EU by 2050.

As Europeans spend an average of 80-90% of their time indoors [23], improvements to the built environment can help to substantially reduce heat stress. Buildings are long-lasting structures and, if appropriately designed, can help to protect their occupants from the impacts of heatwaves and rising temperatures. On the other hand, when buildings overheat, indoor air temperatures can reach levels that negatively affect the health of occupants via heatstroke, dehydration, the aggravation of chronic and respiratory diseases, and even death.

Current studies reveal that 9-20% of the population might be affected by overheating in buildings in several EU countries [24]. However, further data are needed. Low thermal performance and poor building quality can contribute to overheating risks and uncontrolled increasing energy consumption for cooling. Most of the EU's building stock was constructed before thermal standards were introduced, and nearly 75% of the stock is energy inefficient. In 2020, between 5% and 39% of the population, depending on the Member State, lived in dwellings with leaking roofs, damp walls, floors or foundations, or rot in window frames or floors, according to Eurostat.

Newly constructed or renovated buildings can also overheat, even if they are well insulated. This can occur if building design does not adequately consider the combination of solar gains, internal gains and ventilation strategies. Nearly half of city hospitals and schools are in areas with strong UHI effects, thus exposing their vulnerable users to high temperatures [23].

Therefore, overheating in European buildings is not only a comfort issue, but also – and increasingly – a climate, health and social justice issue. While all of Europe faces the impact of higher temperatures in summer, people's level of exposure is very unevenly distributed across population subgroups and areas. Moreover, the elderly, the very young, those with pre-existing medical conditions, pregnant women and socially isolated individuals are more vulnerable to heat.

In nearly all European countries, a lower socio-economic status also increases vulnerability to heat stress. This is often related to living in housing that is more prone to overheating and to difficulties in affording cooling solutions. In many European countries, vulnerable communities tend to live in dense, urban environments and, therefore, may be exposed to higher temperatures due to UHI effects.

The EU strategy on adaptation to climate change (EU adaptation strategy) recognises the negative impacts of heatwaves on the economy, and on the health and well-being of Europeans, and promotes the implementation of physical solutions in response. The strategy includes references to buildings. It also recognises the need for 'just resilience' to ensure that the benefits of climate adaptation are widely and equitably shared.

As with adaptation actions and social considerations, local and municipal governance levels are crucial. However, many local climate adaptation actions focus on technology interventions without taking social characteristics into account [24]. The EU initiative, "Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change" and the other documents of European Commission⁹ [25], which is supporting more than one hundred European regions and communities towards climate resilience by 2030, may help in that respect. The initiative will foster the development of innovative solutions to adapt to climate change and will encourage regions, cities, and communities to lead societal transformation.

⁹ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission>

7. Conclusion and recommendations for BIOBUILD project

The overall objectives of the BIOBUILD project are important to the future adaptation to climate change of residential and office building from EU, and this has resulted in a strong commitment by partners involve to drive the execution of the project. In this regard, there is a high likelihood of sustainability of project activities, and the future of the project is well grounded in EU development and policy.

Climate extremes already take a physical and human toll on the EU region and global climate change will make the situation worse. A “wait and see” attitude to climate change is no longer tenable and “no regrets” adaptation measures need to be implemented now.

The following recommendations emerged out of the discussions with WP1 partners and aimed to provide guidance for the implementation of the project:

- Adaptation of buildings implies achieving thermal comfort by modifying the environment or behaviour based on the expectations and thermal preferences of the occupant, which is otherwise mentioned as thermal adaptation. Adaptive thermal comfort models support the variable indoor temperature standards dealing with the adaptive capacity of occupants. These models help to enhance occupant comfort, reduce energy use, and encourage climate-responsive design of buildings. At the same time, static models deal with fixed indoor temperature standards and support mechanical heating or cooling indoors. The differences in both models formed the context for “thermal adaptation,” which is a combined effect of behavioural, physiological, and psychological processes. Psychological or habituation involves a changed perception of sensory information. Behavioural or technological changes to heat balance include personal adjustment to clothing, activity, postures, food, moving to different locations, modifying surroundings to open or close windows, using HVAC controls, and cultural adjustments such as activity scheduling, dress codes, or siestas.
- Through the use of passive strategies and technologies and renewable energy, new and transformed buildings can save energy and environmental protection, reduce carbon emissions, and even become positive energy buildings to provide power for the grid. It has both environmental and economic benefits. This is crucial. More specifically, from the perspective of the sustainable development goals set by the EU directives, the measures for buildings to cope with climate change will help to achieve the goals: clean water and sunshine, sustainable and clean energy, sustainable cities and communities, responsive consumption and production, climate action.
- Hand in hand with passive strategies is the use of low-carbon materials. The new version of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), approved last March 2024, extends to the entire building life cycle the requirement to reduce GHG emissions until decarbonisation of the sector by 2050. This requirement, which will be measured by the global warming factor, involves considering emissions due to the manufacture of building materials. These emissions will have to be reduced to zero by mid-century, which is a major challenge for the materials used in today's buildings. In order to achieve the above, the involvement of all partners in the project is required – from the architects, through the materials suppliers and contractors to the end user, whose objective is not only to reduce emissions but also to improve the health of users.
- Task 6.1 will consider the selection of climates and cities and the corresponding representative weather data files. The Task 6.1 will define the scope for conducting the dynamic building performance simulations.

References

- [1] UN Environment Programme – *Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction*, 2022. ISBN No: 978-92-807-3984-8. Available online: https://globalabc.org/sites/default/files/2022-11/FULL%20REPORT_2022%20Buildings-GSR_1.pdf
- [2] Alexey Remizov, Shazim Ali Memon, Jong R. Kim, *Climate Zoning for Buildings: From Basic to Advanced Methods—A Review of the Scientific Literature*, MDPI AG, Basel, Switzerland. Available online: <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-5309/13/3/694>
- [3] Li M., Shi J., Guo J., Cao J., Niu J., Xiong M., *Climate Impacts on Extreme Energy Consumption of Different Types of Buildings*, 2015 Available online: <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0124413>
- [4] T. Centofantia, J.M. Hollisb, S. Blenkinsop, H.J. Fowlerc, I. Truckella, I.G. Dubusd, S. Reichenbergere, *Development of agro-environmental scenarios to support pesticide risk assessment in Europe*, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/23282248_Development_of_agro-environmental_scenarios_to_support_pesticide_risk_assessment_in_Europe
- [5] Yehan Wu, Bardia Mashhoodi, Agnès Patuano, and others, *Heat-prone neighbourhood typologies of European cities with temperate climate*, in *Sustainable Cities and Society Journal*, December 2022.
- [6] Beck, H.E., Zimmermann, N. E., McVicar, T. R., Vergopolan, N., Berg, A., & Wood, E. F., *Present and future Köppen-Geiger climate classification maps at 1-km resolution*, *Nature Scientific Data*. DOI:10.1038/sdata.2018.214
- [7] Y.M.R. Allen, O.P. Dube, W. Solecki, F. Aragón–Durand, W. Cramer, S. Humphreys, and others, *Framing and Context*, in: *Global warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the,* Cambridge University Press, 2018.
- [8] https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Heating_and_cooling_degree_days_-_statistics&stable=0
- [9] ***, *European climate zones and bioclimatic design requirements*, PVSITES-WP2-T21-D22_M03-BEAR-20160831-v01.doc
- [10] Thomas Boermans, Carsten Petersdorff, *U-Values for better energy performance of buildings*, ECOFYS GmbH, Germany
- [11] ***, *ECOHEATCOOL: European Heating and Cooling Market Study*. Euroheat & Power, 2016.
- [12] Jarek Kurnitski, Stefano Paolo Corgnati, Tiziana Buso, Andrei Vladimir Litiu, *NZEB definitions in Europe*, REHVA Journal, 2014
- [13] ***, *Encyclopedia of Energy*, Volume 6., Elsevier Inc. , 2004
- [14] <https://www.ecophon.com/uk/about-ecophon/functional-demands/thermal-comfort/>
- [15] S.P. Corgnati, M. Gameiro da Silva, R. Ansaldi, E. Asadi, J.J. Costa, M. Filippi, J. Kaczmarczyk, and others, *Indoor climate quality assessment – evaluation of indoor thermal and indoor air quality*, Rehva Guidebook 14. Rehva, Brussels, 2011.
- [16] Fanger O., *Thermal Comfort*, Copenhagen 1970.
- [17] ***, SR EN ISO 7730:2006 - *Ergonomics of the thermal environment – Analytical determination and interpretation of thermal comfort using calculation of the PMV and PPD indices and local thermal comfort criteria*,

- [18] ***, ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55 - *Thermal Environmental Conditions for Human Occupancy*, American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers: Atlanta, GA, USA , 2023 Edition
- [19] ***, ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 169-2021; *Climatic Data for Building Design Standards*. American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers: Atlanta, GA, USA, 2021 Edition.
- [20] Knut Blind, Luzie Kromer, Peter Neuhäusler, Daniele Rosenberg, Torben Schubert, *European Standardisation Panel Survey* , Edited by: Federica Baldan and Gergely Tardos, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission, March 2024
- [21] Lorenz, A.; Raven, M.; Blind, K. (2019): *The Role of Standardization at the Link between Product and Process Development in Biotechnology*, *The Journal of Technology Transfer* 44, pag.1097-1133.
- [22] Kathrina Simonen, *Life Cycle Assessment*, ROUTLEDGE, London, UK, 2014
- [23] ***, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/household-air-pollution-and-health>
- [24] Denia Kolokotsa, Nikos Kampelis, *Smart Buildings, Smart Communities and Demand Response*, ISTE Ltd, London, UK, 2020.
- [25] ***, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52024DC0091>
- [26] ***, <https://libguides.ccnneb.edu/climatechange>
- [27] A. Hermelink et al., *Towards nearly zero-energy buildings Definition of common principles under the EPBD Final report Panel of international experts*, 2013. [Online]. Available: www.ecofys.com
- [28] M. Kottek, J. Grieser, C. Beck, B. Rudolf, and F. Rubel, *World Map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification updated*, *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 259–263, Jul. 2006, doi: 10.1127/0941-2948/2006/0130.
- [29] ***, “Meteonorm.” [Online]. Available: <http://www.meteonorm.com/>
- [30] V. Palomba, E. Borri, A. Charalampidis, A. Frazzica, S. Karellas, and L. F. Cabeza, *An Innovative Solar-Biomass Energy System to Increase the Share of Renewables in Office Buildings*, *Energies* (Basel), vol. 14, no. 4, p. 914, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.3390/en14040914.
- [31] M. C. Peel, B. L. Finlayson, and T. A. McMahon, *Updated world map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification*, *Hydrol Earth Syst Sci*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 1633–1644, Oct. 2007, doi: 10.5194/hess-11-1633-2007.
- [32] B. Atanasiu, J. Maio, D. Staniaszek, and I. Kouloumpi, *Overview of the EU-27 Building Policies and Programs Factsheets on the Nine Entranze Target Countries: Cross-Analysis on Member-States’ Plans to Develop their Building Regulations Towards the NZEB Standard*, ENTRANZE Project, EACI, Brussels, Belgium, 2012.
- [33]*** *TABULA WebTool*. Accessed: Feb. 12, 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://webtool.building-typology.eu/#bm>
- [34] C. Dipasquale et al., *D2. 1c Simulation Results of Reference Buildings*, EC FP7 project iNSPIRe, Grant agreement, no. 314461, 2014.
- [35] European Commission, *Eurostat database, European Commission: Energy consumption in households by type of end-use*. [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- [36] A. Gevorgian et al., *European Building Stock Analysis. A country by country descriptive and comparative analysis of the energy performance of buildings*, Bozano, Italy, 2021.
- [37]*** *EU Building Stock Observatory from European Commission*, 2017. Accessed: Feb. 12, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/buildings/eubuildings>

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Annex 1

European standards (CEN) selected for BIOBUILD project

No.	Technical committee (TC)	Standard/ Project Reference	Standard Title	Keywords	Abstract/Scope
1	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 13162:2012 +A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made mineral wool (MW) products - Specification	Mineral wool	This European Standard specifies the requirements for factory made mineral wool products, with or without facings or coatings, which are used for the thermal insulation of buildings. The products are manufactured in the mat blankets, boards or slabs. Products covered by this standard are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. This standard describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. Products with a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.25 m ² K/W or a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.06 W/(m K) at 10°C are not covered by this standard. This standard does not cover in situ insulation products (covered by EN 14064 parts 1 and 2) and products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations (covered by EN 14303).
2	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 13168:2012 +A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood wool (WW) products - Specification	Wood wool	This European Standard specifies the requirements for factory made wood wool (WW) products, with or without facings or coatings, which are used for the thermal insulation of buildings. The products are manufactured in the form of boards or slabs. This European Standard also specifies the requirements for the factory made composite products, made from wood wool in combination with other insulation materials. This European Standard describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. Products covered by this European Standard are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels and classes required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. Products with a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.15 m ² K/W or a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.1 W/(m K) at 10°C are not covered by this standard. This European Standard does not cover in situ insulation products and products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations.

3	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 13169:2012 +A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made expanded perlite board (EPB) products - Specification	Perlite board	This European Standard specifies the requirements for factory made expanded perlite board products, with or without facings or coatings, which are used for the thermal insulation of buildings. The products are manufactured in the form of boards, multi-layered insulation or composite insulation products. This standard also covers composite insulation products (see Annex E). Products covered by this standard are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. This standard describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. Products with a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.15 m ² K/W or a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.07 W/(m K) at 10°C are not covered by this standard. This standard does not cover in situ insulation products and products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations.
4	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 13170:2012 +A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made products of expanded cork (ICB) - Specification	Expanded cork	This European Standard specifies the requirements for factory made products of expanded cork, which are used for the thermal insulation of buildings. The products are made with granulated cork agglomerated without additional binders and are delivered as boards with or without facings or coatings. Products covered by this standard are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. This standard describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. Products with a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.25 m ² K/W, or a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.06 W/(m K), at 10°C, are not covered by this European Standard.
5	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 13171:2012 +A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification	Wood fiber	This European Standard specifies the requirements for factory made wood fibre (WF) products, with or without facings or coatings, which are used for the thermal insulation of buildings). The products are manufactured in the form of rolls, batts, felts, boards or slabs. Products covered by this standard are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. This standard describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The classes and levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. Products with a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.2 m ² K/W or a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.07 W/(m K) at 10°C are not covered by this standard. This standard does not cover in situ insulation products and products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations.

6	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 13172:2012	Thermal insulation products - Evaluation of conformity	Insulation products	This European Standard specifies the procedures and the criteria for the evaluation of the conformity of a thermal insulating product with the relevant European product specification. This European Standard applies to factory made products for buildings, factory made products for building equipment and industrial installations, in-situ products for buildings, in-situ products for building equipment and industrial installations and to external thermal insulation composite systems.
7	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 13500:2003	Thermal insulation products for buildings - External thermal insulation composite systems (ETICS) based on mineral wool - Specification	Mineral wool	This European Standard specifies the requirements for factory made products for external thermal insulation composite systems (ETICS) based on mineral wool, delivered as a kit, and used as thermal insulation for buildings. The standard describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, marking and labelling. ETICS are applied to external surfaces of new or existing walls and/or soffits to improve the thermal insulation. ETICS include special fittings (base profiles, corner profiles, etc.) to connect them to adjacent building structures (apertures, corners, parapets, etc.). ETICS give protection against weathering and improve the appearance of the buildings. They do not contribute the stability of the wall and/or soffits on which they are installed. The standard covers systems where the thermal insulation material is required for the load transfer to the substrate. This standard covers systems with a declared thermal resistance equal to or greater than 1 m ² K/W. The requirements from national regulations concerning the mechanical resistance and stability of ETICS should be taken into account. This standard does not cover the strength between the ETICS and the building surface to which it shall be fixed, i. e. the substrate.
8	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14063-1:2004	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed expanded clay lightweight aggregate products - Part 1: Specification for the loose-fill products before installation	Expanded clay	This European Standard specifies the requirements for loose-fill expanded clay lightweight aggregate products for in-situ installation in roofs, ceilings, floors and ground floors. This Part 1 of the standard is a specification for the insulation products before installation. This Part 1 of the standard also describes the product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, marking and labelling. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This standard does not specify performance requirements for airborne sound insulation and for acoustic absorption applications.

9	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14063-1:2004/AC:2006	Thermal insulation products - In-situ formed expanded clay lightweight aggregate products - Part 1: Specification for the loose-fill products before installation	Expanded clay	This European Standard specifies the requirements for loose-fill expanded clay lightweight aggregate (LWA) products installed in roofs, ceilings, floors and ground floors. This Part 2 is a specification for the installed product. Part 2 of this European Standard describes, when taken together with Part 1, the product characteristics that are linked to the essential requirements of the EU Construction Products Directive. Part 2 also specifies the checks and tests to be used for the declarations made by the installer of the product. Part 2 of this European Standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in national regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not cover factory made expanded clay lightweight aggregate products or in-situ products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations. This European Standard does not specify performance requirements for airborne sound insulation and for acoustic absorption applications.
10	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14063-2:2013	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed expanded clay lightweight aggregate products - Part 2: Specification for the installed products	Expanded clay	

11	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14064-1:2018	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed loose-fill mineral wool (MW) products - Part 1: Specification for the loose-fill products before installation	Mineral wool	This document specifies the requirements for blown and injected loose-fill mineral wool products for in situ installation in lofts, masonry cavity walls and frame constructions. This document is a specification for the insulation products before installation. It describes the product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, marking and labelling. This document does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. NOTE To avoid water penetration in masonry walls special tests adjusted to local climate might be needed. This document does not cover factory made mineral wool (MW) insulation products or in situ products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations. Products with a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.25 m ² K/W or a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.06 W/(m K) at 10°C are not covered by this document. This document does not cover products intended for airborne sound insulation and for acoustic absorption applications.
12	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14064-2:2010	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed loose-fill mineral wool (MW) products - Part 2: Specification for the installed products	Mineral wool	This European Standard specifies the requirements for blown loose-fill mineral wool products installed in lofts, masonry cavity walls and frame constructions. This European standard is a specification for the installed insulation products. This European standard describes, when taken together with Part 1 of EN 14064, the product characteristics that are linked to the essential requirements of the EU Construction Products Directive. It also specifies the checks and tests to be used for the declarations made by the installer of the product and the rules for the evaluation of conformity. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. For example, see the note in the scope of Part 1 of EN 14064 regarding the possibility of special water penetration tests in different Member States. Products with a declared thermal conductivity at 10°C greater than 0.06 W/(m K) are not covered by this standard. This European Standard does not cover factory made mineral wool products in the form of mats, batts, rolls or boards. This standard does not cover products intended for airborne sound insulation and for acoustic absorption applications.

13	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14303:2015	Thermal insulation products for building equipment and industrial installations - Factory made mineral wool (MW) products - Specification	Mineral wool	This European Standard specifies the requirements for factory made mineral wool products, which are used for the thermal insulation of building equipment and industrial installations with an operating temperature range of approximately 0°C to +800°C. Below an operating temperature of ambient, special means against water vapour diffusion and water accumulation by air flow might be required. Below an operating temperature of -50°C, special tests regarding the suitability of the products in the intended application are advised (e.g., liquefaction of oxygen). Manufacturer's advice should be heeded in all cases. The products are manufactured with or without facings or coatings, in the form of rolls, boards, slabs, mats, felts, quilts, wired mats, lamella mats, bevelled lags and pipe sections. This European Standard describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. Products covered by this standard are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. This European Standard does not specify the required level of a given property that should be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application can be found in regulations and invitations to tender. Products with a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.065 W/(m K) at 10°C are not covered by this standard. This European Standard does not cover products for in situ insulation (blowing or pouring) or products for the insulation of the building structure. This European Standard does not cover the following acoustical aspects: direct airborne sound insulation and impact noise transmission index.
14	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14316-1:2004	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ thermal insulation formed from expanded perlite (EP) products - Part 1: Specification for bonded and loose-fill products before installation	Expanded perlite	This European Standard specifies the requirements for expanded perlite products for in-situ installation in roofs, ceilings, walls and floors. This Part 1 of the standard is a specification for the insulation products before installation covering the five product types, Perlite Aggregate (EPA), Coated Perlite (EPC), Bitumen Coated Perlite (EPB), Hydrophobic Perlite (EPH) and Premixed Perlite (EPM). Part 1 of this European Standard describes the product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not cover factory made insulation products of formed shapes and boards made with expanded perlite. The products covered by this standard are not intended to be used primarily for airborne sound insulation or sound absorption applications although they may improve the performance of the buildings in these respects when installed for their primary thermal insulation intended use.

15	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14316-2:2007	Thermal insulating products for buildings - In-situ thermal insulation formed from expanded perlite (EP) products - Part 2: Specification for the installed products	Expanded perlite	This European Standard specifies the requirements covering the four product types of expanded perlite products Perlite Aggregate (EPA), Coated Perlite (EPC), Hydrophobic Perlite (EPH) and Premixed Perlite (EPM), containing less than 1% organic material as defined by annex D of prEN 14316-1:2002 for in-situ insulation of roofs, ceilings, walls and floors. This Part 2 of the standard is a specification for the installed products. This Part 2 of this standard contains specifies the checks and test procedures to be used for the declaration made by the installer of the product. This European Standard does not specify the required level of all properties to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The required levels are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not include factory made insulation products of formed shapes and boards made with expanded perlite or in-situ products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations. This European Standard does not specify performance requirements for airborne sound insulation and for acoustic absorption applications.
16	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14317-1:2004	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ thermal insulation formed from exfoliated vermiculite (EV) products - Part 1: Specification for bonded and loose-fill products before installation	Exfoliated vermiculite	This European Standard specifies the requirements for the four types of exfoliated vermiculite products Vermiculite Aggregate (EVA), Coated Vermiculite (EVC), Hydrophobic Vermiculite (EVH) and Premixed Vermiculite (EVM), containing less than 1% organic material as defined by annex D for in-situ insulation of roofs, ceilings, walls and floors. This Part 1 of this standard is a specification for the insulation products before installation. This Part 1 of this standard describes the product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. This European Standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not cover factory made insulation products of formed shapes and boards made with exfoliated vermiculite or in-situ products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations. This European Standard does not specify performance requirements for airborne sound insulation and for acoustic absorption applications.

17	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 14317-2:2007	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ thermal insulation formed from exfoliated vermiculite (EV) products - Part 2: Specification for the installed products	Exfoliated vermiculite	This European Standard specifies the requirements for the four types of exfoliated vermiculite products Vermiculite Aggregate (EVA), Coated Vermiculite (EVC), Hydrophobic Vermiculite (EVH) and Premixed Vermiculite (EVM), containing less than 1% organic material as defined by Annex D of EN14317-1:2004 for in-situ insulation of roofs, ceilings, walls and floors. This Part 2 of the standard is a specification for the installed products. This Part 2 of this standard also specifies the checks and test procedures to be used for the declaration made by the installer of the product. This European Standard does not specify the required level of all properties to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The required levels are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not include factory made insulation products of formed shapes and boards made with exfoliated vermiculite or in-situ products intended to be used for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations. This European Standard does not specify performance requirements for airborne sound insulation and for acoustic absorption applications.
18	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 15101-1:2013+A1:2019	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed loose fill cellulose (LFCI) products - Part 1: Specification for the products before installation	Cellulose	This European Standard specifies requirements for loose-fill cellulose insulation (LFCI) products for the thermal and/or sound insulation of buildings when installed into walls, floors, galleries, roofs and ceilings. This European Standard is a specification for the loose-fill cellulose insulation (LFCI) products before installation. This European Standard describes the product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, marking and labelling and the rules for evaluation of conformity. Products covered by this European Standard may also be used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the structural performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. Products with a declared thermal conductivity at 10°C greater than 0.06 W/(m K) or a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.25 m ² K/W are not covered by this European Standard. This European Standard does not specify the required level of all properties to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The required levels are to be found in local regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not cover factory made cellulose products placed on the market as bats, mats or boards intended to be used for the insulation of buildings or loose-fill cellulose products for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations.

19	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 15101-2:2013	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed loose fill cellulose (LFCI) products - Part 2: Specification for the installed products	Cellulose	This European Standard specifies requirements for in-situ formed loose-fill cellulose insulation (LFCI) products when installed as thermal insulation into walls, floors, galleries, roofs, lofts and ceilings. This Part 2 is a specification for the installation checks for the installed products. It specifies the checks and tests to be used for the declarations made by the installer of the product. This European Standard does not specify the required level of all properties to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The required levels are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. Products with a declared thermal conductivity at 10°C (mean temperature) greater than 0.06 W/(m K) or a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.25 m ² K/W are not covered by this European Standard. This European Standard does not cover factory made cellulose mats, bats or quilts intended to be used for the insulation of buildings or in-situ cellulose products for the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations. Nor does it specify performance requirements.
20	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 15501:2015	Thermal insulation products for building equipment and industrial installations - Factory made expanded perlite (EP) and exfoliated vermiculite (EV) products - Specification	Expanded perlite, exfoliated vermiculite	This European Standard specifies the requirements for factory made expanded perlite and exfoliated vermiculite products which are used for the thermal insulation of building equipment and industrial installations with an operating temperature in the range of approximately 0°C to +1 100°C. Expanded perlite and exfoliated vermiculite products can be used below 0°C but special tests regarding the suitability of the product in the intended application are advised (e.g., liquefaction of oxygen). Manufacturer's advice should be heeded in all cases. The products are manufactured in the form of boards, pipe sections, segments, prefabricated ware and special ware. This European Standard describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. Products covered by this European Standard are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the structural performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. This European Standard does not specify the required level of a given property that is achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application can be found in regulations and invitations to tender. Products with a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.6 W/(m K) at 10°C are not covered by this European Standard. This European Standard does not cover products intended to be used for the insulation of the building structure. The European Standard does not cover the following acoustical aspects: direct airborne sound insulation and impact transmission noise index.

21	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 15599-1:2010	Thermal insulation products for building equipment and industrial installations - In-situ thermal insulation formed from expanded perlite (EP) products - Part 1: Specification for bonded and loose-fill products before installation	Expanded perlite	This European Standard specifies the requirements for expanded perlite products which are used for the thermal insulation of building equipment and industrial installations with an operating temperature in the range of approximately -270°C to +650°C. This European Standard specifies the requirements for the four types of expanded perlite products Perlite Aggregate (EPA), Coated Perlite (EPC), Hydrophobic Perlite (EPH) and Premixed Perlite (EPM), containing less than 1% by mass organic material as determined by Annex C. This European Standard is a specification for the insulation products before installation. This European Standard describes the product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. This European Standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not cover factory made insulation products of formed shapes and boards made with expanded perlite, and does not cover products intended to be used for the insulation of buildings. The products covered by this standard are not intended to be used primarily for airborne sound insulation or sound absorption applications although they may improve the performance of the installation in these respects when installed for their primary insulation intended use.
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22	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 15599-2:2010	Thermal insulation products for building equipment and industrial installations - In-situ thermal insulation formed from expanded perlite (EP) products - Part 2: Specification for the installed products	Expanded perlite	<p>This European Standard specifies the requirement for expanded perlite products which are used for in-situ thermal insulation of building equipment and industrial installations with an operating temperature in the range of approximately -270°C to $+650^{\circ}\text{C}$. This European Standard specifies the requirements for the four types of expanded perlite products, Perlite Aggregate (EPA), Coated Perlite (EPC), Hydrophobic Perlite (EPH) and Premixed Perlite (EPM), containing less than 1 % by mass organic material as determined by Annex C in EN 15599-1:2010. This European Standard is a specification for the installed products. This European Standard also specifies the checks and test procedures to be used for the declaration made by the installer of the product. This European Standard does not specify the required level of all properties to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The required levels are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not include factory made insulation products of formed shapes and boards made with expanded perlite. The products covered by this European Standard are not intended to be used primarily for airborne sound insulation or sound absorption applications although they may improve the performance of the installation in these respects when installed for their primary insulation intended use.</p>
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23	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 15600-1:2010	Thermal insulation products for building equipment and industrial installations - In-situ thermal insulation formed from exfoliated vermiculite (EV) products - Part 1: Specification for bonded and loose-fill products before installation	Exfoliated vermiculite	This European Standard specifies the requirements for exfoliated vermiculite products which are used for the thermal insulation of building equipment and industrial installations with an operating temperature in the range of approximately -40°C to +1 050°C. This European Standard specifies the requirements for the four types of exfoliated vermiculite products Vermiculite Aggregate (EVA), Coated Vermiculite (EVC) Hydrophobic Vermiculite (EVH) and Premixed Vermiculite (EVM), containing less than 1 % by mass organic material as determined by Annex C. This European Standard is a specification for the insulation products before installation. This European Standard describes the product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling. This European Standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not cover factory made insulation products of formed shapes and boards made with exfoliated vermiculite, and does not cover products intended to be used for the insulation of buildings. The products covered by this standard are not intended to be used primarily for airborne sound insulation or sound absorption applications although they may improve the performance of the installations in these respects when installed for their primary insulation intended use.
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24	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 15600-2:2010	Thermal insulation products for building equipment and industrial installations - In-situ thermal insulation formed from exfoliated vermiculite (EV) products - Part 2: Specification for the installed products	Exfoliated vermiculite	This European Standard specifies the requirement for exfoliated vermiculite products, which are used for in-situ thermal insulation of building equipment and industrial installations with an operating temperature in the range of approximately -40°C to +1 050°C. This European Standard specifies the requirements for the four types of exfoliated vermiculite products Vermiculite Aggregate (EVA), Coated Vermiculite (EVC), Hydrophobic Vermiculite (EVH) and Premixed Vermiculite (EVM), containing less than 1% by mass organic material as determined by Annex C in EN 15600-1:2010. This European Standard is a specification for the installed products. This European Standard also specifies the checks and test procedures to be used for the declaration made by the installer of the product. This European Standard does not specify the required level of all properties to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The required levels are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards. This European Standard does not include factory made insulation products of formed shapes and boards made with exfoliated vermiculite. The products covered by this European Standard are not intended to be used primarily for airborne sound insulation or sound absorption applications although they may improve the performance of the installation in these respects when installed for their primary insulation intended use.
25	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	EN 15732:2012	Light weight fill and thermal insulation products for civil engineering applications (CEA) - Expanded clay lightweight aggregate products (LWA)	Expanded clay	This standard describes the product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, marking and labelling. This European Standard specifies the requirements for loose-fill expanded clay lightweight aggregate (expanded clay LWA) products for Civil Engineering Applications excluding the use as thermal insulation in and under buildings which are covered by EN 14063-1. The standard covers the use of expanded clay LWA as lightweight fill and insulation materials in embankments for roads, railways and other trafficked areas and as lightweight backfill for structures. This standard does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application are to be found in regulations or non-conflicting standards.

26	CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products	FprEN 17139	Thermal insulation products for building - Factory made vegetal fibres based products (VFBP)	Vegetal fibres	This document specifies the characteristics for factory made vegetal fibres based products (VFBP), with or without facings or coatings and with or without integral reinforcement, which are used for thermal insulation of buildings. Products are manufactured in form of rolls, felts or boards. Products covered by this standard can also be used for acoustic applications. The standard also covers multi-layered boards. Products covered by this standard are also used in prefabricated insulating systems. The structural performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered by this standard. This document applies to any thermal insulation products made of at least 70% of vegetal fibres per mass with or without the addition of bonding agents or bonding fibres and/or additives and which don't fall within the scope of the EN 13171. It does not replace the existing procedures for the determination of the declared properties of products already covered by an existing harmonized standard. Products with a declared thermal conductivity at 10°C, greater than 0.07 W/(m K) or a declared thermal resistance lower than 0.2 m ² K/W are not covered by this standard. This standard does not cover in situ applied insulation and products intended to be used in the insulation of building equipment and industrial installations.
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Annex 2

ISO standards for BIOBUILD

No	Technical committee (TC)	Sub-comm. (SC), Working Group (WG)	Standard/project reference	Standard title	Key words	Abstract/Scope	Standard status and category
1	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO 6334: 2023	Thermal insulation products for building equipment and industrial installations — Expanded perlite products — Specification	Expanded perlite	<p>This document specifies the requirements for factory-made expanded perlite products which are used for thermal insulation of industrial installations and building equipment with an operating temperature from 23°C to ~1 000°C. The products are manufactured in the form of boards, pipe sections, segments, prefabricated ware and special ware.</p> <p>This document describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity, marking and labelling.</p> <p>Products covered by this document are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the structural performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered.</p> <p>This document does not specify the required level or class of a given property required to be achieved by a product in order to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application. The levels required for a given application can be found in regulations and invitations to tender.</p> <p>This document is not applicable to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) products with a declared thermal conductivity greater than 0.072 W/(m K) at 70°C; b) products intended to be used for the insulation of the building structure; c) the acoustical aspects; <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) direct airborne sound insulation, and 2) impact noise transmission index. 	Published basic standard

2	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO 8144-1:1995	Thermal insulation — Mineral wool mats for ventilated roof spaces — Part 1: Specification for applications with restricted ventilation	Mineral wool	Specifies the properties and acceptable tolerances for bonded mineral wool thermal insulating mats. Provides limiting values for most of the properties; design values may be derived from these. The mats specified are for use within ventilated roof spaces of buildings where the ventilation of the roof space may be restricted. The mats shall not change their properties and are dimensionally stable for the temperature and humidity conditions within a ventilated roof.	Published basic standard
3	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO 8144-2:1995	Thermal insulation — Mineral wool mats for ventilated roof spaces — Part 2: Specification for horizontal applications with unrestricted ventilation	Mineral wool	Specifies the properties and acceptance tolerances for bonded mineral wool thermal insulating mats. The mats specified are only intended to be used for horizontal applications with unrestricted ventilation and are not designed to support any applied load.	Published basic standard
4	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO 8145:1994	Thermal insulation — Mineral wool board for overdeck insulation of roofs — Specification	Mineral wool	Specifies the properties and acceptable tolerances as well as limiting values for most of them for bonded man-made mineral wool board for the overdeck insulation of roofs of buildings. The product is intended for roofs carrying foot traffic by maintenance personnel only. The properties to be declared by the manufacturer at the time of delivery are specified, as are some test methods for the determination of these properties. Caution should be exercised in using test results as design values.	Published basic standard

5	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO 17749: 2018	Thermal insulation products — Sheep wool mat and board — Specification	Sheep wool	This document specifies requirements for factory-made products of sheep wool, which are used for the thermal insulation of buildings. This document applies to material containing more than 50% (by mass) natural sheep wool, with the balance being polymeric material. The products are delivered as a mat or board with or without facings. This document describes product characteristics and testing methods, marking, labelling and packaging. Products covered in this document are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. The sheep wool mat and board thermal insulation is not to be used when the continuous service temperature of the substrate is outside the range of -60°C to +80°C. The use of mothproof agent residues is outside the scope of this document. This document does not address all the health and safety aspects associated with its use. It is the responsibility of the user of this document to establish appropriate health and safety practices.	Published basic standard
6	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO 22482: 2021	Thermal insulation products — Aerogel blanket for buildings — Specification	Aerogel blanket	This document specifies the requirements for factory-made aerogel blankets, which are used for the thermal insulation of building applications. This document specifies insulation that exhibits thermal insulating performance through high porosity and nano-sized pores by compounding aerogel with net-like fibrous material, e.g., polyester, glass fibre, ceramic fibre. The products are delivered as a blanket type. This document describes product characteristics and includes procedures for testing, evaluation of conformity and marking and labelling. This document does not specify the required level of a given property to be achieved by a product to demonstrate fitness for purpose in a particular application.	Published basic standard

7	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO 24260: 2022	Thermal insulation products — Hemp fiber mat and board — Specification	Hemp fiber	This document specifies requirements for factory-made products of hemp fibre, which are used for the thermal insulation of buildings. This document applies to material containing more than 50% (by mass) natural hemp fibre, with or without the other natural fibre and the balance being polymeric material. The products are delivered as a mat or board with or without facings. This document describes product characteristics and testing methods, marking, labelling and packaging. Products covered in this document are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels. The performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. The use of moth proof agent residues is outside the scope of this document. This document does not address the health and safety aspects associated with its use. It is the responsibility of the user of this document to establish appropriate health and safety practices.	Published basic standard
8	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO/CD 8144-1	Thermal insulation — Mineral wool mats for ventilated roof spaces — Part 1: Specification for applications with restricted ventilation	Mineral wool	Specifies the properties and acceptable tolerances for bonded mineral wool thermal insulating mats. Provides limiting values for most of the properties; design values may be derived from these. The mats specified are for use within ventilated roof spaces of buildings where the ventilation of the roof space may be restricted. The mats shall not change their properties and are dimensionally stable for the temperature and humidity conditions within a ventilated roof.	Under development, project
9	ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment	ISO/TC 163/SC 3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems	ISO/CD 8144-2	Thermal insulation — Mineral wool mats for ventilated roof spaces — Part 2: Specification for horizontal applications with unrestricted ventilation	Mineral wool	Specifies the properties and acceptance tolerances for bonded mineral wool thermal insulating mats. The mats specified are only intended to be used for horizontal applications with unrestricted ventilation and are not designed to support any applied load.	Under development, project

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10	ISO/TC 165 Timber structures		ISO/DIS 7567	Bamboo structures — Glued laminated bamboo — Product specifications	Bamboo	This document specifies product specification for glued laminated bamboo: requirements for components and bonding, performance requirements of glued laminated bamboo products, production and storage facilities, evaluation of conformity and marking and labelling.	Under development, project
11	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO 9239-1:2010	Reaction to fire tests for floorings Part 1: Determination of the burning behaviour using a radiant heat source		ISO 9239-1:2010 specifies a method for assessing the wind-opposed burning behaviour and spread of flame of horizontally mounted floorings exposed to a heat flux radiant gradient in a test chamber, when ignited with pilot flames. This method is applicable to all types of flooring. e.g., textile carpet, cork, wood, rubber and plastics coverings as well as coatings. Results obtained by this method reflect the performance of the flooring, including any substrate if used. Modifications of the backing, bonding to a substrate, underlay or other changes of the flooring may affect test results. ISO 9239-1:2010 is applicable to the measurement and description of the properties of floorings in response to heat and flame under controlled laboratory conditions. It should not be used alone to describe or appraise the fire hazard or fire risk of floorings under actual fire conditions.	Published basic standard

12	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO/DIS 9239-1	Reaction to fire tests for floorings Part 1: Determination of the burning behaviour using a radiant heat source	This part of ISO 9239 specifies a method for assessing the wind-opposed burning behaviour and spread of flame of horizontally mounted floorings exposed to a heat flux radiant gradient in a test chamber, when ignited with pilot flames. Annex A gives details of assessing the smoke development, when required. This method is applicable to all types of flooring, e.g. textile carpet, cork, wood, rubber and plastics coverings as well as coatings. Results obtained by this method reflect the performance of the flooring, including any substrate if used. Modifications of the backing, bonding to a substrate, underlay or other changes of the flooring may affect test results. This part of ISO 9239 is applicable to the measurement and description of the properties of floorings in response to heat and flame under controlled laboratory conditions. It should not be used alone to describe or appraise the fire hazard or fire risk of floorings under actual fire conditions. Information on the precision of the test method is given in Annex B.	Under development, project
13	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO 5657: 1997	Reaction to fire tests Ignitability of building products using a radiant heat source	ISO 5657:1997 provides a detailed methodology for testing the ignitability of building products using a radiant heat source, helping to ensure that materials used in construction meet necessary fire safety standards. The results obtained from this test method are used to assess the fire performance of building products, which is crucial for ensuring safety in building design and construction. It helps manufacturers and regulators to classify materials based on their ignitability and contribute to fire safety regulations and standards. Understanding the ignitability of building materials is essential for fire risk assessment and management. The ISO 5657:1997 standard provides a reliable and standardized method for evaluating this property, contributing to safer building practices and improved fire safety in construction.	Published basic standard

14	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO 5658-2:2006	Reaction to fire tests Spread of flame Part 2: Lateral spread on building and transport products in vertical configuration	ISO 5658-2:2006 specifies a method of test for measuring the lateral spread of flame along the surface of a specimen of a product orientated in the vertical position. ISO 5658-2:2006 provides data suitable for comparing the performance of essentially flat materials, composites or assemblies that are used primarily as the exposed surfaces of walls in buildings and transport vehicles, such as ships and trains. Some profiled products (such as pipes) can also be tested under specified mounting and fixing conditions. ISO 5658-2:2006 is applicable to the measurement and description of the properties of materials, products or assemblies in response to radiative heat in the presence of a pilot flame under controlled laboratory conditions. ISO 5658-2:2006 is not suitable to be used alone to describe or appraise the fire hazard or fire risk of materials, products or assemblies under actual fire conditions.	Published basic standard
15	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO 5658-2:2006/ Amd 1:2011	Reaction to fire tests Spread of flame Part 2: Lateral spread on building and transport products in vertical configuration Amendment 1	ISO 5658-2:2006/Amd 1:2011 provides important updates and clarifications to the original standard, enhancing the test method for determining the lateral spread of flame on vertically oriented building and transport products. This contributes to improved fire safety assessment and regulation adherence. The updates in this amendment apply to the original scope of ISO 5658-2:2006, which deals with the lateral spread of flame on building and transport products in a vertical configuration. The amendment ensures that the test results are more reliable and applicable to current industry standards. Amendments like ISO 5658-2:2006/Amd 1:2011 are crucial for maintaining the relevance and accuracy of standardized test methods. By incorporating the latest technical advancements and addressing any ambiguities, this amendment helps in better assessing fire safety and performance of materials, leading to safer building practices and regulatory compliance.	Published amendment

16	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO 9705-1:2016	Reaction to fire tests Room corner test for wall and ceiling lining products Part 1: Test method for a small room configuration	<p>ISO 9705-1:2016 specifies the test method to evaluate the reaction of wall and ceiling products to fire when installed at the surface of a small room and exposed directly to a specified ignition source. The test represents a fire scenario, which starts under well-ventilated conditions in a corner of a specified room with a single open doorway.</p> <p>Tests performed in accordance with the method specified in this part of ISO 9705 provide data for the early stages of a fire from ignition up to flashover. The method does not evaluate the fire resistance of products.</p> <p>The method is not intended to evaluate floor coverings. This method is not suitable for sandwich panel building systems, pipe insulation and façades for which specific ISO standards (i.e. ISO 13784, ISO 20632 and ISO 13785, respectively) are available.</p>	Published basic standard
17	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO/TS 3814:2014	Standard tests for measuring reaction-to-fire of products and materials Their development and application	<p>ISO/TS 3814:2014 describes the relevance of, and how to apply, the fire tests developed by ISO/TC 92/SC 1 so that they can be used effectively to reduce the hazard of fire. Each reaction-to-fire test is related to the different phases of a developing fire in buildings and transport and has to be seen in its relation to the fire scenario and phase of the fire it represents. Some reaction-to-fire tests are proposed to assess the fire hazard in those different phases.</p> <p>Although ISO/TS 3814:2014 does not address smouldering combustion, this does not mean that smouldering is not important in some fire development situations. However, there are no tests in Subcommittee 1 (SC 1) which currently address this phenomenon.</p> <p>ISO/TS 3814:2014 is aimed at indicating those ISO tests which produce relevant and useful data for fire safety engineering and those which do not. ISO/TS 3814:2014 is also of use to regulators, people who are performing reaction-to-fire tests including manufacturers and all people who are responsible to create, control, and assess fire safety concepts.</p>	Published, technical specification

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18	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO 5660-1:2015	Reaction-to-fire tests. Heat release, smoke production and mass loss rate. Part 1: Heat release rate (cone calorimeter method) and smoke production rate (dynamic measurement.)	Reaction-to-fire	ISO 5660-1:2015 specifies a method for assessing the heat release rate and dynamic smoke production rate of specimens exposed in the horizontal orientation to controlled levels of irradiance with an external igniter. The heat release rate is determined by measurement of the oxygen consumption derived from the oxygen concentration and the flow rate in the combustion product stream. The time to ignition (sustained flaming) is also measured in this test. The dynamic smoke production rate is calculated from measurement of the attenuation of a laser light beam by the combustion product stream. Smoke obscuration is recorded for the entire test, regardless of whether the specimen is flaming or not.	Published basic standard
19	ISO/TC 92 Fire safety	ISO/TC 92/SC 1 Fire initiation and growth	ISO 5660-1:2015/ Amd 1:2019	Reaction-to-fire tests. Heat release, smoke production and mass loss rate. Part 1: Heat release rate (cone calorimeter method) and smoke production rate (dynamic measurement.) Amendment 1	Reaction-to-fire	ISO 5660-1:2015/Amd 1:2019 provides important updates and clarifications to the original ISO 5660-1:2015 standard, enhancing the test method for determining the heat release rate of materials using a cone calorimeter. The updates in this amendment apply to the scope of ISO 5660-1:2015, which deals with the measurement of the heat release rate of materials using the cone calorimeter method. This method is widely used to evaluate the fire behavior of building products, including their heat release rate, smoke production, and mass loss rate. Amendments like ISO 5660-1:2015/Amd 1:2019 are critical for keeping standardized test methods up-to-date with technological advancements and industry needs. By refining the test procedures and clarifying ambiguities, this amendment helps ensure that the heat release rate and related properties of materials are measured more accurately and consistently, leading to better fire safety assessments and compliance with safety regulations.	Published amendment

20	ISO/TC 43 Acoustic	ISO/TC 43/SC 2 Building acoustics	ISO 10534- 2:2023	Acoustics. Determination of acoustic properties in impedance tubes. Part 2: Two- microphone technique for normal sound absorption coefficient and normal surface impedance	Acoustic	<p>This test method covers the use of an impedance tube, two microphone locations and a frequency analysis system for the determination of the sound absorption coefficient of sound absorbing materials for normal incidence sound incidence. It can also be applied for the determination of the acoustical surface impedance or surface admittance of sound absorbing materials. As an extension, it can also be used to assess intrinsic properties of homogeneous acoustical materials such as their characteristic impedance, characteristic wavenumber, dynamic mass density and dynamic bulk modulus.</p> <p>The test method is similar to the test method specified in ISO 10534-1 in that it uses an impedance tube with a sound source connected to one end and the test sample mounted in the tube at the other end. However, the measurement technique is different. In this test method, plane waves are generated in a tube by a sound source, and the decomposition of the interference field is achieved by the measurement of acoustic pressures at two fixed locations using wall-mounted microphones or an in-tube traversing microphone, and subsequent calculation of the complex acoustic transfer function and quantities reported in the previous paragraph. The test method is intended to provide an alternative, and generally much faster, measurement technique than that of ISO 10534-1. Normal incidence absorption coefficients coming from impedance tube measurements are not comparable with random incidence absorption coefficients measured in reverberation rooms according to ISO 354. The reverberation room method will (under ideal conditions) determine the sound absorption coefficient for diffuse sound incidence. However, the reverberation room method requires test specimens which are rather large. The impedance tube method is limited to studies at normal and plane incidence and requires samples of the test object which are of the same size as the cross-section of the impedance tube. For materials that are locally reacting only, diffuse incidence sound absorption coefficients can be estimated from measurement results obtained by the impedance tube method (see Annex E).</p>	Published basic standard
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21	ISO/TC 218 Timber		ISO 17959: 2014	General requirements for solid wood flooring	Wood flooring	ISO 17959:2014 specifies the requirements and test methods of characteristics of solid wood flooring boards for internal (interior) use as flooring. It also specifies packaging and marking requirements. It is applicable to both finished and unfinished solid wood flooring board. Solid wood parquet is not covered.	Published basic standard
22	ISO/TC 207 Environment management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14046: 2014	Environ. management. Water footprint. Principles, requirements and guidelines		ISO 14046:2014 specifies principles, requirements and guidelines related to water footprint assessment of products, processes and organizations based on life cycle assessment (LCA). ISO 14046:2014 provides principles, requirements and guidelines for conducting and reporting a water footprint assessment as a stand-alone assessment, or as part of a more comprehensive environmental assessment. Only air and soil emissions that impact water quality are included in the assessment, and not all air and soil emissions are included. The result of a water footprint assessment is a single value or a profile of impact indicator results. Whereas reporting is within the scope of ISO 14046:2014, communication of water footprint results, for example in the form of labels or declarations, is outside the scope of ISO 14046:2014.	Published basic standard

